

RSU21

Cardiff
Metropolitan
University

Prifysgol
Metropolitan
Caerdydd

Cardiff Metropolitan University

Cardiff School of Management

MBA

**An Assessment on Factors Influencing the Healthcare Service Quality
A Case Study on Divisional Hospital-Palai OPD Services, Killinochchi District,
Sri Lanka**

Submitted in

February 2022

By

Kanagaratnam Pakeerathan

Student ID - 20192703– ICBT ID- CL/CARDIFFMB/21/454

**This dissertation is submitted in
partial fulfillment of the
requirements for the Degree of
Master of Business Administration (MBA) in Health Sector Management**

Turnitin Originality Report

Digital Receipt

This receipt acknowledges that Turnitin received your paper. Below you will find the receipt information regarding your submission.

The first page of your submissions is displayed below.

Submission author: Kanagaratnam Pakeerathan
Assignment title: MBA 7099 Dissertation Submission (Moodle PP)
Submission title: 20192703 RSU21.docx
File name: 79890_Kanagaratnam_Pakeerathan_20192703_RSU21_12501...
File size: 12.4M
Page count: 83
Word count: 11,825
Character count: 68,908
Submission date: 20-Feb-2022 03:42AM (UTC+0000)
Submission ID: 171420594

20192703 RSU21.docx

ORIGINALITY REPORT

5 %	1 %	1 %	3 %
SIMILARITY INDEX	INTERNET SOURCES	PUBLICATIONS	STUDENT PAPERS

PRIMARY SOURCES

1	Submitted to University of Wales Institute, Cardiff Student Paper	2 %
2	Miguel Ángel Ortíz Barrios. "Redesigning the Barranquilla's public emergency care network to improve the patient waiting time", Universitat Politecnica de Valencia, 2020 Publication	1 %
3	Xingxia Kou, Zhen Peng, Meigen Zhang, Ning Zhang, Lili Lei, Xiujuan Zhao, Shiguang Miao, Ziming Li, Qiuji Ding. " Assessment of the Meteorological Impact on Improved PM Air Quality Over North China During 2016–2019 Based on a Regional Joint Atmospheric Composition Reanalysis Data - Set ", Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres, 2021 Publication	<1 %
4	www.socialresearchfoundation.com Internet Source	<1 %
5	Submitted to The Robert Gordon University Student Paper	<1 %

6	Submitted to Asia e University Student Paper	<1 %
7	ir.mu.ac.ke:8080 Internet Source	<1 %
8	Submitted to University of South Australia Student Paper	<1 %
9	centenary.dspacedirect.org Internet Source	<1 %
10	www.jourlib.org Internet Source	<1 %
11	GA Thomson, A Medagama, A Dissanayake, D Lenora, W Kumarihamy, P Bushby, D Weremczuk, MW Hirst, DJS Fernando. "Pandemic diabetes: can developed-world health professionals do more to support care in developing countries?", European Diabetes Nursing, 2015 Publication	<1 %
12	dev.saxinstitute.org.au Internet Source	<1 %
13	eprints.usm.my Internet Source	<1 %
14	etd.aau.edu.et Internet Source	<1 %

DECLARATION

This work is being submitted in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of **Master of Business Administration (MBA) in Health Sector Management** and has not previously been accepted in substance for any degree and is not being concurrently submitted in candidature for any degree.

Signed

Dr. Kanagaratnam Pakeerathan

(Candidate)

Date: 28th February, 2022

SUPERVISOR'S DECLARATION STATEMENT

From: myresearch.supervisor@gmail.com

To: kkpakeerathan@gmail.com

Date: Tue, Feb 22, 2022 at 7.53 PM

To:

Research Unit

Post graduate division, ICBT

SUPERVISOR'S DECLARATION STATEMENT (MBA-RSU21)

Student Name - Kanagaratnam Pakeerathan

Supervisor's Name - Mr. Ragukumar S. Thanganathan

Hereby I acknowledge that the above-named student has regularly attended the supervision meetings, and actively engaged in the dissertation supervision process.

This, also acknowledges the dissertation meeting records and the filed ethical exemplar forms are authentic and correct.

Best regards,

Ragukumar S. Thanganathan

MBA (Merit-Cardiff Met), MSc.IT (Distinction-Cardiff Met),
BIT (UoC), MBCS, CIMA Cert BA.

Senior Lecturer (IT & Management) |

Consultant Higher Education Management & Academic Affairs

Mobile: +94-77-236-5-461

Email: ragukumar@gmail.com

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

Foremost, I would like to express my sincere gratitude to my Supervisor Mr. Ragukumar S. Thanganathan (Senior Lecturer and Consultant in Higher Education Management & Academic Affairs) for the continuous support of my MBA research, for his patience, motivation, enthusiasm, and his outstanding immense knowledge.

I have also appreciated him at this juncture, for his very fine quality that he possesses, a very strict Principles on Research Culture & Code of Ethics with friendly manner he has instilled those qualities in me, which enabled me to find my own potential. His guidance helped me in all the time of research and writing of this thesis and has shown genuine interest in my progress. I could not have imagined having a better advisor and mentor for this study.

Besides my advisor, it would have been impossible to come to this journey without the support from lecturers who taught me throughout this program. I want to thank the ICBT Family, including Lecturers, Staff and friends.

My sincere thanks go to RDHS Killinochchi, Divisional Hospital Palai Health Staff and Patients, who has helped me carry out this research & to collect survey data in Pandemic situations.

Last but not least, I would like to thank my family for giving their remarkable support during this very crucial period and encouraging me in this endeavor.

Dedication

I was empty, now filled, hope in future is fulfilled

By the Grace of Lord Krushna,

With Love

This works is Dedicated to

Mrs. Sivakowri Pakeerathan

Master Aran Pakeerathan

My Parents, Siblings;

&

Dr.N. Saravanabhavan

RDHS, Kilinochchi

Abstract

This empirical research was conducted to assess the Influencing factors in the context of healthcare services of OPD of Divisional Hospital Palai, Killinochchi District, Sri Lanka, due to the significant decline of OPD patients for the last few years with multiple public complaints made on various media.

After the careful and detailed extensive study of existing literature reviews, the researcher has identified the five most commonly affecting independent factors in healthcare services: tangibility, assurance, reliability, responsiveness, & empathy, critically influencing Perceived service quality. Based on the conceptual framework researcher has generated a hypothesis and tested the correlation between identified all five independent variables with Perceived service quality.

Data were collected from sample 374 OPD patients through the pretested questionnaire, which was designed based on the operationalization with adequate specific indicators to measure each variable. A simple random sampling method was practiced to collect the data to maintain uniformly generalized responses.

The study has found that tangibility & assurance has a positive & moderate relationship with perceived service quality, whereas, reliability, responsiveness and empathy have a positive and strong relationship with perceived service quality individually. Also discovered that assurance and responsiveness are statistically insignificant predictors to service quality in the combined model even though Pearson's correlation validated the individual relationship with service quality.

Based on the findings, the researcher has provided necessary feasible recommendations to improve the adequate improvement in perceived service quality of OPD services at DH Palai via Skills, Training on safety measures, fund & human resource allocation specifically to Northern Province Healthcare Administrators such as PDHS, RDHS & Stakeholders. The objective of this research has accomplished as the study has identified the five critical factors that affect the perceived service quality, the Level of Influence Critical Factors on Perceived Services Quality, measured the Level of Current OPD Care services, Evaluating the level of confidence patient's Intention of using the OPD and abled to provide the needed recommendation.

Key words: Perceived Service Quality, OPD, PDHS, RDHS, Healthcare, Tangibility, Assurance, Reliability, Responsiveness, Empathy.

Table of Contents

Page Number

Turnitin Originality Report	i
Declaration.....	iii
Acknowledgement	iv
Dedication	v
Abstract.....	vi
List of Tables	xi
List of Figure	xii
1 Chapter One.....	1
1.1 Introduction	1
1.1.1 Background of the Study	1
1.2 The Research Problem Identification	2
1.2.1 Symptoms & Signs.....	2
1.3 Justification of the Problem.....	3
1.3.1 OPD Visits	3
1.3.2 Inadequate Human Resources.....	4
1.3.3 Health Issues of Staff During Pandemic Covid 19.....	6
1.3.4 Health Staffs Protest & Strikes	7
1.4 Defining Research Problems.....	7
1.4.1 Research Questions	7
1.4.2 Research Objectives	7
1.5 Significance of the Study	8
1.6 Limitation of Study.....	9
1.7 Chapter Outline	10
2 Chapter Two	11
2.1 Critical Review of Literature	11
2.1.1 Brief Discussion on Service Quality in Health Sector	11
2.1.2 Patients Perception & Service satisfaction in OPD Services.....	11
2.1.3 Importance of Quality Care & Safety of the Services	12
2.1.4 Evolution the Patient-oriented healthcare services	12

2.1.5	Theories as Backbone on Implementing the Service Quality	13
2.2	Critical Reviews towards the Conceptual Framework	14
2.3	Empirical Literature & Formulation of Variables through key theme analysis ..	16
2.3.1	Tangibility	16
2.3.2	Assurance	17
2.3.3	Reliability	18
2.3.4	Responsiveness.....	19
2.3.5	Empathy	20
2.3.6	Service Quality (Dependent Variable).....	21
2.3.7	Socio-Demographic Variables	21
2.4	Literature Summary	23
2.5	Literature Mapping.....	24
3	Chapter Three.....	27
3.1	Research Methodology	27
3.1.1	Formulated Conceptual Framework of this study.....	27
3.2	Operational Definitions.....	28
3.2.1	Tangibility	28
3.2.2	Assurance	28
3.2.3	Reliability	28
3.2.4	Responsiveness.....	28
3.2.5	Empathy	28
3.3	Development of Hypothesis.....	29
3.4	Operationalization.....	30
3.5	Design of Modified SERVQUAL Questionnaire	32
3.5.1	Research Design.....	32
3.5.2	Questionnaire.....	32
3.5.3	Research Onion (Appendix 6)	32
3.5.4	Research Philosophy: Positivism.....	33
3.5.5	The approach of Research: Deductive.....	33
3.5.6	Research Strategy: Survey.....	33
3.5.7	Research Choice: Mono method.....	33
3.5.8	Research Time Frame: Cross-Sectional	33
3.6	Data Collection Methods: SERVQUAL Questionnaire	34
3.6.1	Sample Design.....	34
3.6.2	Population	34

3.6.3	Sample selection Procedure	34
3.6.4	Sample Size.....	35
3.7	Data Collection Method	35
3.8	Research Data Analysis Techniques	36
4	Chapter Four	37
4.1	Introduction to Statistical Analysis.....	37
4.1.1	The Data Interpretation & Presentation	37
4.1.2	Analysis of Socio Demographic Data of Respondents	37
4.2	The Reliability Test of the gathered Data.....	43
4.3	Descriptive Statistics Analysis of Collected Data.....	46
4.3.1	Skewness.....	47
4.3.2	The Kurtosis Test of this research	47
4.4	Multicollinearity Test.....	48
4.5	Frequency Table for Questionnaire `s Responses.....	49
4.6	Hypothesis Testing.....	59
4.6.1	Testing Hypothesis H1.....	60
4.6.2	Testing Hypothesis H2.....	62
4.6.3	Testing Hypothesis H3.....	63
4.6.4	Testing Hypothesis H4.....	65
4.6.5	Testing Hypothesis H5.....	66
4.7	Outline of the Correlation of the Variables.....	68
4.8	Exploration of Multiple-Linear Regression	69
4.9	Proposed New Model excluding Assurance and Responsiveness	71
4.10	Final Report of Hypothesis	73
5	Chapter Five	74
5.1	Conclusion & Suggestion	74
5.1.1	Summary of Study	74
5.1.2	Research Conclusion	75
5.2	Recommendation	79
5.2.1	Recommendation to Improve the Tangibility	79
5.2.2	Recommendation to Improve the Assurance	80
5.2.3	Recommendation to Improve the Reliability	80
5.2.4	Recommendation to Improve the Responsiveness.....	80
5.2.5	Recommendation to Improve the Empathy	81
5.3	Suggestions & Future Research	83

6	References	xiii
7	Appendix 1: Questionnaire	xix
8	Appendix 2: Questionnaire (Tamil Version).....	xxvi
9	Appendix 3: Research Permission & Approval	xxxiii
10	Appendix 4: Minutes of the Mandatory Supervisors Meeting	xxxiv
11	Appendix 5: Ethical Application Form	xxxv
12	Appendix 6: Saunders’s Research Onion	xl
13	Appendix 7: Healthcare Delivery Model in Sri Lanka.....	xli

List of Tables

Table 1: Annual OPD Visits	4
Table 2: Human Resources of DH Palai	5
Table 3.1: Literature Summary	23
Table 3.2: Literature Mapping	24
Table 3.3: Literature Mapping	25
Table 3.4: Literature Mapping	26
Table 4.1: Operationalization	30
Table 4.2: Operationalization	31
Table 5: Five Point Likert`s scale for Questionnaire	36
Table 6.1: Reliability of Variables	43
Table 6.2: Reliability of Variables	44
Table 7: The Thumb rule for Cronbach`s Alpha value	44
Table 8: Cronbach's Alpha for given variable	45
Table 9: The Scale of All Variables	45
Table 10: Statistics of Descriptive Variable	46
Table 11: The Descriptive statistics of Skewness & Kurtosis	47
Table 12: Skewness Rule	47
Table 13: The Variable Inflation Factors (VIF) of each variable of this study	48
Table 14.1: Frequency Responses of all the Variables	49
Table 14.2: Frequency Responses of all the Variables	50
Table 14.3: Frequency Responses of all the Variables	51
Table 14.4: Frequency Responses of all the Variables	52
Table 14.5: Frequency Responses of all the Variables	53
Table 14.6: Frequency Responses of all the Variables	54
Table 14.7: Frequency Responses of all the Variables	55
Table 14.8: Frequency Responses of all the Variables	56
Table 14.9: Frequency Responses of all the Variables	57
Table 15: Rule of Correlation	59
Table 16: Statistics of Correlation between Tangibility and Service Quality	60
Table 17: Statistics of Correlation between Assurance and Service Quality	61
Table 18: Statistics of Correlation between Reliability and Service Quality	63
Table 19: Statistics of Correlation between Responsiveness and Service Quality	65
Table 20: Statistics of Correlation between Empathy and Service Quality	67
Table 21: Correlation Variables report	68
Table 22: The Variables Entered & Model Report for all variables	69
Table 23: ANOVA: All variables	70
Table 24: Coefficients: All variables	70
Table 25: Coefficients for All variables in New Model	71
Table 26: ANOVA for All variables in New Model	72
Table 27: Report of Hypothesis Test Table	73

List of Figures

Figure 1: Organization of the health system in Sri Lanka	1
Figure 2: Line Graph of OPD Visits	4
Figure 3: Human Resources of DH Palai	5
Figure 4: OPD visits VS Doctors	5
Figure 5: Covid 19 Positive in Staff	6
Figure 6: Quarantine of Staff	6
Figure 7: Parasuraman, Zeithaml and Berry's model	14
Figure 8: Service recovery Paradox after effective management	18
Figure 9: Literature Review Summary	22
Figure 10: Conceptual Model of Hypotheses	27
Figure 11: Calculated Sample Size	35
Figure 12: Gender	37
Figure 13: Age Group	38
Figure 14: Marital Status	38
Figure 15: Education	39
Figure 16: Area of Living	39
Figure 17: Employment	40
Figure 18: Number of Children	40
Figure 19: Duration of Works	41
Figure 20: OPD Visits	41
Figure 21: Monthly Income	42
Figure 22.1: Frequency Responses of all the Variables in Bar Chart	58
Figure 22.2: Frequency Responses of all the Variables in Bar Chart	59
Figure 23: The Scatter graph: Tangibility and Service Quality	61
Figure 24: The Scatter graph: Assurance and Service Quality	62
Figure 25: The Scatter graph: Reliability and Service Quality	64
Figure 26: The Scatter graph: Responsiveness and Service Quality	66
Figure 27: The Scatter graph: Empathy and Service Quality	67

1 Chapter One

1.1 Introduction

1.1.1 Background of the Study

1.1.1.1 General View of the Sri Lankan Health Care System

According to its national policy, Sri Lanka has exhibited outstanding free public healthcare services. One of the best free healthcare services in developing countries, and according to the Family Health Bureau, Sri Lanka, its Infant Mortality Rate (IMR) in 2020 is 8.0 (Family Health Bureau, 2020). IMR is one of the best indicators to assess health services globally, and Sri Lanka has remained excellent as developed countries such as the United States of America, where its IMR is 6.5 (Unicef, 2021). As WHO has globally recommended on Resilient Health Operating System by formulating national healthcare policies with adequate long-term sustainable strategies and developing those into reasonable & achievable action (WHO, 2010),

It is observable that Divisional Hospitals in Sri Lanka have played a significant role in health services, including OPD services. (Refer Appendix 7)

Figure 1: The Organization of the healthcare system in Sri Lanka
Source: (WHO, 2010) : (Smith, 2017)

1.1.1.2 Overview of Divisional Hospital Palai, Killinochchi, Sri Lanka

Divisional Hospital (DH) Palai is one of the Primary health care institutions providing curative care to the people of Pacchilaipalli in Killinochchi District, Sri Lanka. DH Palai has extended its services to the other closest places, such as Maruthenkeni, in Jaffna District. (Ministry of Health, 1994).

Due to the growing population in Sri Lanka, the Pachchilaipalli population is also significantly growing, currently; the estimated population of the Pacchilaipalli will be around 14504 in November 2021 (Ministry of Home Affairs & Divisional Secretariat Pachchilaipalli, 2021).

According to the available minutes of RDHS Killinochchi, cadre allocation for DH Palai was revised in 2013 to improve the Human Resources, and after that, implementation has not taken place to uphold the sustainability of the health care services.

According to the Census in 2012, the total population of Pacchilaipalli was 8510, with a population density of 52/ km² (Department of Census & Statistics, 2012). Its standard of service should not be compromised at any cost and, if not sustained as recommended, eventually shall lead to deterioration of overall healthcare of the public in Pacchilaipalli.

1.2 The Research Problem Identification

1.2.1 Symptoms & Signs

1.2.1.1 Declining of OPD Patient's enrolments

According to the hospital statistics, OPD services were significantly improved from 2013 to 2018. During this period, patients who used the OPD services increased from 15904 in 2013 to 40524 in 2018. From 2019, decline features of using OPD Services by patients will be observed. It was very much lowered & reached in 2021 as 13500 (District Secretariat-Killinochchi, 2021).

1.2.1.2 Patient & Complaints

Many Patients have verbally complaint to our hospitals' staff on Poor Service Quality, and many News Papers, social media (Mirror, 2020) also have made continuous criticism on poor Service quality of DH Palai & (TodayJaffna, 2020), which has significantly

influenced the researcher to choose this area to assess factors influencing the healthcare service quality of the DH Palai's OPD services (Nakarvu, 2022).

1.2.1.3 Poor Infrastructure

Another concern for this study is that Infrastructure of the DH Palai has not been adequately designed as per the standard laid by the Health Ministry since OPD Premises have been constructed by the American Pacific Command & which has a significant impact on the hospital's performance (Hospital Minutes, RDHS).

1.3 Justification of the Problem

1.3.1 OPD Visits

Islandwide public health services are hugely dependent on these health institutions. Fruitful usage of these health institutions sometimes has been underused by the public and bypasses the services of primary care institutions and reach secondary or tertiary care providing centers (Ministry of Health, 2018).

Eventually, this pattern of practice of patients throughout the country significantly impacts higher intuitions such as NHSL, Teaching Hospitals. One of the reasons for the underuse of health services in Primary care settings and overuse of health resources and services from Secondary or tertiary institutions depends on the Pattern of Service provided through those institutions (Perera & Perera, 2017).

Reducing OPD usage by patients can play a huge role in other hospital services. Eventually, it will further affect the inward admission, Clinic follow-ups & other relevant healthcare services. If the OPD service is not improved at least to the acceptable level, it can affect the healthcare services & further decline demand for DH Palai.

Because State fund allocation for the hospital would be deteriorative and improving the grading of the hospital would be at risk (Internal Expert Opinion). Such as Allocation of the Fund, Annual Transfer of Medical Officer to DH Palai, Demand for Nursing Officers, Midwives, Attendants & HAS appointments to the hospital would be delayed unnecessarily. This shall significantly influence service quality & the overall performance of the hospital.

Summary of Data 2013-2021 DH Palai –OPD Visits

Year	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
OPD Visits	15904	20836	27302	32882	36436	40524	38518	20814	13500

Table 1: Annual OPD Visits

Figure 2, illustrates the considerable decline in the OPD usage by patients.

Figure 2: Line Graph of OPD Visits

This could be due to a variety of existing factors, including no adequate human resources, emerging of new private clinics in Pacchilaipalli, poor availability of infrastructures, lack of responsiveness, lack of empathy towards the patients, inadequate safety practices, time & queuing, the poor effective operation management of OPD, lack of equity preferences with poor patient-centred services (District Secretariat-Killinochchi, 2021).

1.3.2 Inadequate Human Resources

Human Resources of DH Palai, especially Medical Officers, are not adequate as required with the growing population & plays a crucial role in Service Quality & Performance of the Hospital.

Staffs	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
Doctors (MO)	1	3	3	2	1	2	1	1
Dental Doctors	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1
Nursing officers	1	1	0	1	0	3	3	3
PHM	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1
Minor Staffs	15	15	16	18	15	14	11	12

Table 2: Human Resources of DH Palai

Figure 3: Human Resources of DH Palai

Figure 4: OPD visits VS Doctors

Even though prevailing pandemic Covid 19 has restricted the traveling needs of the patients, it could have negatively affected the patients to use the hospital for their medical problems. Studies have shown that Covid 19 significantly played in OPD usage by patients (Chatterji & Li, 2020). Similarly, it has affected the health staff as well.

1.3.3 Health Issues of Staff During Pandemic Covid 19

Many staff during the pandemic have been affected by Covid 19 significantly and have been quarantined accordingly; it could have significantly affected the Service provided.

Figure 5: Covid 19 Positive in Staff

Figure 6: Quarantine of Staff

1.3.4 Health Staffs Protest & Strikes

Different categories of health staff are constantly doing the demanded strikes or protest throughout the years, but these are significantly increased during the last two years; even during the pandemic, Health Supportive staff, Nurses and Doctors have made frequent strikes for financial burden, which has obviously had an impact on service quality.

1.4 Defining Research Problems

Service Quality depends on many factors; in healthcare services, it is greatly supported by proper infrastructure, adequate human resources & the attitude of the staff while considering the betterment of patient care. In DH Palai, a study has observed a significant decline of OPD patients, Patient's complaints about poor services & staff, understaffed, poor infrastructure.

This study will help to full fil the Patient's expectation, more precisely, perceived service quality at OPD of DH Palai is a collective result of the above factors; hence, it is crucial to **Assess and Identify the factors affecting the Service Quality of OPD at DH Palai, Killinochchi, Sri Lanka.**

1.4.1 Research Questions

- I. What are the critical factors affecting the perceived service quality of OPD patient care?
- II. What level of influence each of the identified factors individually and collectively has on the perceived service quality of OPD patient care at Palai hospital?
- III. To what degree those critical factors are presently fulfilled at Palai hospital OPD?
- IV. How the perceived service quality affects the Patient's Intention to use the OPD care services?
- V.

1.4.2 Research Objectives

- I. Identify the Critical Factors affecting perceived Service Quality of OPD Patients
- II. Identify the Level of Influence Critical Factors on Perceived Services Quality of OPD care at DH Palai
- III. Measure the Level of Current OPD Care services at DH Palai
- IV. Evaluating the level of confidence patient`s Intention of using the OPD at DH Palai
- V. To formulate the Recommendation to improve the Overall perceived service quality of OPD at DH Palai.

1.5 Significance of the Study

Quality of services has been provided according to the expectation of patients. It also ensures the customer`s satisfied services. It has a crucial role in sustainable health services (Velmurugan, et al., 2019). Primary healthcare institutions are transforming, and the Government of Sri Lanka is taking steps to strengthen its primary health care services. It has also launched the Primary Health Care System Strengthening Project for Sri Lanka (PSSP) with the support of the world bank.

It has been observed that DH Palai provides excellent health services with limited resources available compared to other peripheral regions (District Secretariat-Killinochchi, 2021).

Therefore, studying Services quality of Out Patient Department (OPD) Services at DH Palai shall contribute to the further development of better care services and eventually help to improve the Quality of services of other Primary care services in Killinochchi District.

We could concentrate more on improving the patient satisfaction factors, such as Human resources, infrastructure, safety, effectiveness, equity. Empathy, responsiveness, & patient-centred care (Corrigan, 2001) could improve the Quality of the service provided and eventually elevate the hospital's standard from the current stages.

Therefore, this study gives fruitful results to war-affected areas and their people to improve health care. Apart from that, assessing the Quality of services at Primary care institutions are studied limitedly.

Therefore, the service quality of health services and its relevant studies are essential for the sustainability of satisfying customer services (Fatima, et al., 2019). It will ensure the effective services of the Institution. This study could be used by policymakers & researchers to focus on further development and implementation of primary healthcare delivery.

1.6 Limitation of Study

This study was conducted entirely based on a questionnaire survey & limited to OPD services of DH Palai. It does not include the Clinic & Inpatient care services of DH Palai. Therefore, it does not represent the Overall Performance of DH Palai.

Even though qualitative methods are good for assessing patient experiences due to time factors and safety measures during pandemic Covid 19, it is limited to quantitative monotype cross sectional study.

There were not enough studies conducted in Sri Lanka on Service quality at OPD Services in Primary Care institutions like Divisional Hospital using the Questionnaire. Therefore, it prevented the researcher from finding exhaustive previous research materials based on Sri Lankan Primary Healthcare services.

During prevailing pandemic conditions, it could be played in reducing OPD Visits, but the study did not consider assessing its influences; therefore, a separate study on Covid 19 influences in OPD services is needed.

The study did not include the Care giver's perception of service quality; therefore, it is impossible to come to better recommendations and strategies to improve the service quality.

1.7 Chapter Outline

Chapter2: Critical Literature Review

This chapter shall review the literature of research conducted primarily in Sri Lanka and other parts of the world regarding Service Quality in Healthcare Organizations, and it shall further include theories involved and models used.

Chapter 3: Research Methodology

This chapter focuses on & generates the functional conceptual frame layout and is implemented based on relevant literature mapping, and simultaneously research hypotheses were established based on a conceptual framework. Associated Research design, study population, sample design, necessary sample size, adequate data collection method and data analysis techniques were discussed in detail.

Chapter 4: Data Collection and Analysis

This chapter shall analyze the hypotheses by using descriptive and inferential methods. The relationship and effect between the independent and dependent variables were tested by Correlation and Regression analysis through the SPSS tool.

Chapter 5: Conclusion and Recommendation

This chapter shall include the conclusion elaborated by the researcher based on research findings and analysis. The feasible recommendations were discussed in detail to improve the Service Quality in OPD Services of DH Palai. This chapter shall further argue the suggestions for future studies.

2 Chapter Two

2.1 Critical Review of Literature

2.1.1 Brief Discussion on Service Quality in Health Sector

Service Quality is widely accepted that customer satisfaction is the driving force for any organisation`s progressive & sustainable development among its competitors. However, as discussed in the Introduction chapter, IOM has established a specific landmark for patient satisfaction, which leads to patient-oriented better health care & quality of services (Corrigan, 2001). Therefore, it has been highly recommended that sustaining patient satisfaction is the key role in continuing the progressive services (Kohn, et al., 2000; Hurtado, et al., 2001). The principles of IOM on Service quality have been implemented throughout the world to maintain the standard of healthcare practice. However, Sri Lanka has given priority to healthcare services, and it offers free healthcare services compared to other developed countries (Fernando, 2000).

2.1.2 Patients Perception & Service satisfaction in OPD Services

There are many agreements on patient satisfaction; in a nutshell, *Patient satisfaction* is defined as an outcome of their expectations and experiences from service providers (Geberu, et al., 2019).

Expectations are involved with Medical Care, Admission & Discharge Mechanism, Collective services with adequate Social Responsibility (Aagia & Garg, 2010). Similarly, Professionalism, Empathy towards the patients, Infrastructure of the Hospital, Employee's Relationship gives a collective dimension to patients' perception of the overall expectation from the hospital (Arsali, et al., 2008).

According to Wan & Nor (2016), patient satisfaction and expected to follow the sustainability visits for hospital services depend on Tangible, Assurance & Empathy; it is directly associated with Quality of services. Another study conducted in the Sri Lankan context found that patients' perceived Quality of services associated highly with Physical facilities, Responsiveness than professionalism (Wijenayake, et al., 2019).

2.1.3 Importance of Quality Care & Safety of the Services

Institute of Medicine (IOM) in the USA has observed through its publications *Err is Human (1999)* and *Chasing the Quality Chasm (2001)* states that to improve the quality of service with adequate safety measures need to be focused on evidence-based information system (Corrigan, 2001) in the health sector, where patient-centred healthcare service delivery possible to manifest accordingly (Kohn, et al., 2000). Service quality is the fundamental entity for any organisation to persist among competitors.

Lohr from IOM (1992) has clarified and quoted that Service quality & care are known as the “*degree to which health services for individuals and populations increase the likelihood of desired health outcomes and are consistent with current professional knowledge*”.

2.1.4 Evolution the Patient-oriented healthcare services

In the late 1960s, Enid Balint claimed that patient-centred care is contrary to illness-oriented care. Later development occurred during 1970 in the idea of the Physio Psycho-Social Medicine, which put a light on holistic approaches of care where patient-centred care was focused (Gusmano, et al., 2019).

In 1986 Picker foundation influenced the patient-centred Care movement and later evolved as Picker Institute. IOM played a considerable role in patient-centred care through their famous publication mentioned above, including envisioning the National Healthcare Quality Report (Hurtado, et al., 2001) created awareness among the health fraternity.

Both publications identified that one of the crucial factors is patient-centred care, and other highly recognised six domains for aspect is better healthcare is Safe, Effective, timely, efficient & equitable (Corrigan, 2001).

In the Sri Lankan context practicing such doctrines should be incorporated through National Policies. In 2015, the cabinet accepted the National Policy on Healthcare Quality & Safety and monitored it through the Directorate of Healthcare Quality & Safety (DHQS) under the Ministry of Health (DHQS, 2020).

2.1.5 Theories as Backbone on Implementing the Service Quality

In general, a set of theories are involved in defining service quality. For example, Supply chain Theory and Organizational Behavior theory have been used to improve clients Satisfaction (Borkowski & Meese, 2021). Queuing theory is applicable to assess patient flow in OPD services (A.H. Nor Aziati & Binti Hamdan, 2018).

Lean Six Sigma theory to identify the factors influencing Patient-centred care & Culture (Teeling, et al., 2021), Similarly, Total Quality Management (TQM) is an important theory incorporated into service quality in the health sector and extensively studied (Zaid, et al., 2020).

The following three theories are more suitable for this study relevant to principles & functionality of Customer Satisfaction & Service Quality. Those are,

2.1.5.1 Customer Satisfaction Theory (CSAT) is a Landmark

This was initially proposed by Oliver (1980) that Satisfaction is the component that exists as a result of the difference between the Expectation & Perception of the Performance received (Oliver. R. L., 1980).

2.1.5.2 The Expectancy Disconfirmation Paradigm (EDP) Theory

As Oliver in 1977 & 1980 proposed, it is one of the promising theoretical framework models to assess customer satisfaction. In this model, customer expectation level becomes a benchmark for the product produced.

2.1.5.3 The SERVQUAL Model

In 1988, Parasuraman et al, proposed the SERVQUAL Model, which is one of the reliable models ever produced to assess customer satisfaction. Which is assess the customer satisfaction on following main five components & prescribed as Tangibility (4 queries), Responsiveness (4 queries), Assurance (4 queries), Reliability (5 queries) & Empathy (5 queries) (Parasuraman, et al., 1988). (Parasuraman, et al., 1985).

Figure 7: Parasuraman, Zeithaml and Berry’s model (Parasuraman, et al., 1988).
(Rezaei, et al., 2018).

2.2 Critical Reviews towards the Conceptual Framework

As per this argument, Wijenayake, P., V, K., YJ, S. & MDU, G (2019), researchers from the Medical Service Unit, Policy Analysis unit of Education, Training & Research unit, Western Provincial Directors' office use the data from Psychiatric (Study of Mind & Mental Disorders) Clinic of National Hospital of Sri Lanka (NHSL) through the descriptive cross-sectional study by using SERVQUAL Model on patients' perception regarding its service quality care.

They have found that their hypothesis strongly supported **Tangibility** expectation than **Responsiveness**. They have also found out that all the aspects of SERVQUAL need to be improved (Wijenayake, et al., 2019) in the said Clinic.

It has also been observed, they did not modify the SERVQUAL model; it thereby agrees that a similar model is easy to apply effectively to find the correlation between patient satisfaction & service quality.

Another interesting study conducted by Min Li and his team in 2015 used the SERVQUAL model to assess the patient's perception of the service quality at hospitals in China. They have extensively studied both OPD & Inpatients service quality in nine provinces and recommended that demographic variables influence the priorities in components of the SERVQUAL Model. Out of these findings, **Reliability & Tangibility** played a key role in their OPD Service.

Similarly, Older patients, more than 60, were given more credits on **Reliability, Assurance & Empathy** (Li, et al., 2015). This is a unique study conducted in a larger population and able to guide the possible Demographic variable such as Age groups, gender, Area of living (Urban /Village), Marital status, Education Level, Employment, Frequency of Visits & Income status (Zun, et al., 2018).

It is important to consider other service sectors such as the telecommunication Industry. Rengarajan et al. (2019) have used the SERVQUAL Model in this industry to identify the service quality in Kanchipuram District, Tamil Nādu, India.

Their research has considered overall service quality majorly depend on **Assurance & Reliability** for Perception of Customer. It collectively assesses all the aspects of the SERVQUAL model component in favor of service quality (Rengarajan, et al., 2019). The study conducted by Fatima et al. (2019) from the University of Punjab, Lahore, Pakistan & International Center for Health Information Technology have found that the SERVQUAL model has been extensively used in healthcare setup & also found that **Tangibility** is the most common contributing factor in the study of Service quality (Fatima, et al., 2019).

The Researchers from Vellore Institute of Technology, Tamil Nadu, India Velmurugan, G et al (2019) has studied the SERVQUAL Model with Service Quality in Healthcare Organizations found that **all the five components** are crucial & also found that demographic variables are not affecting the perception of Service quality. The patients' educational background played a significant role in SERVQUAL model assessment (Velmurugan, et al., 2019).

One of the interesting studies conducted by Kalubowila, K. C. et al (2017) group of Authors from Post Graduate Institute of Medicine (PGIM), University of Colombo, Colombo South Teaching Hospital (CSTH), General Hospital Kalutara & Base Hospital Panadura Sri Lanka has used the self-administered questionnaire to assess the Patient satisfaction at the OPD services. Using the predetermined scoring system, found overall service of quality at OPD is satisfactory (Kalubowila, et al., 2017).

2.3 Empirical Literature & Formulation of Variables through key theme analysis

2.3.1 Tangibility

In Healthcare, Impression is the first influencing factor for any services (Kalubowila, et al., 2017); infrastructure such as its available physical facilities, technological advancement, Equipment, working professional appearance & communication sources plays a crucial role in tangibility impression towards the customers (Sanjeeva & Senevirathne, 2017) (Arsali, et al., 2008). They state that 41.8% are satisfied with tangibility, tangibility in healthcare considered with possessing a desk, patient examination table, reception, computers, X-rays machine or any equipment. Another study conducted by Punnakitikashem et al defines the similar views as above (Punnakitikashem, et al., 2012).

Any service providing organization is essentially incorporated with tangibility as a prime component to ensure the sustainability of the services (Kalaja, et al., 2016). Zubayer & Hogue also support that tangible dimension plays a significant role in service quality (Zubayer & Hoque, 2019). Emmanuel (2019) claims that tangibility measures the Physical environment of the hospital and directly affects the service quality (Bosompem Boadi, et al., 2019) (Chi & Quan, 2013).

It has also ensured the revisit of the customers to reach the organization. In healthcare services, tangibility as one of the antecedent factors plays a considerable role in Service quality. In other words, tangibility is one of the major components used in the SERVQUAL model (Parasuraman, et al., 1988) and many researchers have identified that tangibility as an individual component played a crucial role in patient perception.

The study conducted by Zun (2018) on service quality at clinics in Malaysia shows that tangibility is the most critical dimension which includes proper attire of the health staff, pleasant look with necessary technology and equipment to pay attention by patients. It also states that Patients were described tangibility need to improve to offer a better service.

Very interestingly, the study has found out that tangibility available at the service place needs to have a piece of better information to its customers than its existence. In other

words, tangibility could be misunderstood by the patients that it exists for further advancement of service rather than the better service quality (Zun, et al., 2018).

Contrast to above, Tantarto (2020) states that in conventional health services, Tangibility is less important compared to modern forms of Telemedicine healthcare service (Tantarto, et al., 2020).

2.3.2 Assurance

Assurance is a continuous process evolved through the best practices available to ensure patient perception via adequate service quality (Ramseook-Munhurrun, et al., 2010) (Kitapci, et al., 2014). As a described component of the SERVQUAL Model, a study conducted by Bedman Narteh (2017) in the Banking sector on service quality validated that Assurance played a significant role in customer satisfaction (Narteh, 2017).

It is a direct proportional factor to standard practice ensured through its services (Li, et al., 2015). In healthcare, Assurance is defined as specialized knowledge, skills & courtesy of the staff (Fatima, et al., 2019) and their genuine interest (Kalubowila, et al., 2017) to inspire the customers with trust & confidence. Quality Assurance gives the overall picture of the customer satisfaction of an organization (Kalaja, et al., 2016) (E.T. Jagoda, et al., 2019).

The organization is responsible for a high standard of service assured to its clients. This is another Antecedent Factor that decide the Service Quality, Assurance is a collective entity of several interlinked components towards the service quality provided (Parasuraman, et al., 1988). According to Bucke (2020) Collective entities in healthcare are confidence. Comfortability and dignified services (Bucke, et al., 2020).

This argument agrees with many researchers and Assurance as a single component plays a significant role in customer satisfaction (McCreddie, et al., 2021). It is well observed in the health sector that word of mouth about hospital services, especially on its Human Resources such as Doctors, Nurses, and other staff. How they offer the services is important to sustain the OPD patients. It will greatly impact loyal patients to the Hospital (Kalaja, et al., 2016), (Li, et al., 2015).

The following graph illustrates how Loyalty to a customer is important for any successful development of the organization. With time it shows that with the help of Loyalty of customers' failure could turn into successful recovery (Howell, 2012).

Figure 8: Service recovery Paradox after effective management (Howell, 2012).

It has also observed from the graph that Loyalty is increasing significantly with Assurance of the service and its s directly affect patient's satisfaction; DH Palai had significant OPD patients, to make them return to use the OPD service as a Loyal Patients DH Palai needs to revisits its erroring factors on service quality. Moreover, study conducted in Nigeria, reveals that assurance as a courteous act towards the customers and also says that staff possessing with required knowledge (Mahmoud, et al., 2019)

2.3.3 Reliability

Reliability has been defined as a service that any organisation promises to offer is dependent on how an organisation has optimised its customs to accurately deliver such promised services (Li, et al., 2015), (Kalaja, et al., 2016). It also needs to ensure error-free information apart from promised service (Sohail, 2003). A fascinating study conducted in the Banking sector on customer loyalty with the working model of SERVQUAL found that Reliability is the leading determinant for loyalty (Wanninayake , et al., 2019).

This is one of the most commonly interpreted Antecedent factors as a deciding factor of Customer Satisfaction via Service Quality in the Study of SERVQUAL Model (Parasuraman, et al., 1988), (Hurtado, et al., 2001), (Arachchi & Kaluarachchi, 2019) , In which it has been assessed through the five queries. This has been extensively studied via SERVQUAL instruments in different industries and validated that Reliability is an essential component to assess the patient's satisfaction (Sohail, 2003) (Bucke, et al., 2020).

In another study, reliability was defined as guaranteed performance of the services (Subiyakto, et al., 2020) (Mosadeghrad, 2012). A similar study conducted by Jagoda et al. (2019) on Service quality on patients' satisfaction in Sri Lanka also validated that through SERVQUAL instruments, the Reliability of Nursing services are playing a massive role in patient satisfaction (E.T. Jagoda, et al., 2019).

Zohreh Anbari et al. (2014) states that the Quality of Hospital services significantly depends on its promises & maintaining the error-free information recording mechanism. In other words, Service quality is directly dependent on Reliability (Anbari, et al., 2014).

2.3.4 Responsiveness

This is defined as how the employees of any organization are ready to assist the customers when they need it (Arsali, et al., 2008), (Bosompem Boadi, et al., 2019), (Bucke, et al., 2020); more precisely, it is the willingness towards prompt services. In healthcare sectors, this attitude is essential for the Hospital staff (Mahmoud, et al., 2019), (Fatima, et al., 2019), (Sathiyaseelan & Gnanapala, 2015). One of the majorly studied antecedent factors in SERVQUAL Model of Parasuraman et al. (1988) to assess the Service Quality via Perceived Patient satisfaction (Parasuraman, et al., 1988).

Kalaja (2016) observed in their Durres Public Hospital Service Quality assessment that Responsiveness towards the patients significantly improves the Quality of Services (Kalaja, et al., 2016). Another validated study conducted by Li (2015), states that age group less than 49 gives importance to Tangibility, whereas the old age category more than 60 years preferred the Empathy & Responsiveness (Li, et al., 2015) and view also supported by (Sadiq Sohail, 2003).

It's also appreciated by Victor Lorin (2013) on the study conducted in the Romanian Public Health Care system to assess the service Quality via SERVQUAL Model that Responsiveness plays a massive role in the functional quality of the service provided (Purcărea, et al., 2013).

2.3.5 Empathy

One of the observed antecedent factors and extensively studied in the service quality discipline (Naik, et al., 2013) (Li, et al., 2015) and (Velmurugan, et al., 2019). SERVQUAL Model of Parasuraman et al (1988) defined the Empathy as how effectively employees of an organization connect with its customers through various modes such as careful listening, Informative Direction, Respectful towards the patients, equity & feeling secured (Parasuraman, et al., 1988).

This argument is supported by study conducted in Sri Lanka on service quality and medical tourism, where Empathy plays huge role in serviced quality (Arachchi & Kaluarachchi, 2019), (Sanjeewa & Senevirathne, 2017), (Kalubowila, et al., 2017) and supported by (Naik, et al., 2013).

Li (2015), observed that patients over 60 years were inclined towards the Empathy rather than Tangibility component. This study was conducted in Nine Province in China, where a sizable aged group of patients exists. This study is very reliable and supports that the SERVQUAL Model is invariably good as other health-related service quality assessment methods (Li, et al., 2015).

Study conducted by Fellani Danasra Dew (2011) on Service Quality in Dental practices to assess the Empathy & Responsiveness using SERVQUAL Model states that Empathy primarily involved with Communication, Attention & Knowledge on Needs (Danasra Dew, et al., 2011).

It further observes that poor quality of services is directly connected with inadequate practice of empathy as mentioned above, most of the patients are dissatisfied with administration due to failure to show Empathy (Danasra Dew, et al., 2011) (Fatima, et al., 2019).

2.3.6 Service Quality (Dependent Variable)

As discussed above, researcher concluded that the Service Quality is a dependent variable of this study and it can be viewed through the Tangibility, Assurance, Reliability, Responsiveness & Empathy. It is crucial to uphold the healthcare service quality get the patients satisfaction (Sathiyaseelan & Gnanapala, 2015), (Kalaja, et al., 2016), (Arsali, et al., 2008) and expect to use the any services continuously as a loyal customer and acceptance of the service provided is another feature of perceived service quality (Li & Shang, 2019), (Bosompem Boadi, et al., 2019).

Convenience is another attribute that patients expect in healthcare service quality providers (KumarRoy, et al., 2018), (Purcărea, et al., 2013). Study conducted in the NHS, UK shows that Patients Complaint can indicate the failure of the Service Quality in hospital (McCreddie, et al., 2021).

Word of Mouth is one of the vital parts and which is the direct marketing by patients without any payment. WOM or recommendation of the healthcare service quality by patients can define the impact of service quality of healthcare service (Kitapci, et al., 2014) (Naik, et al., 2013).

2.3.7 Socio-Demographic Variables

Service Quality is involved with human society; simultaneously, society inculcates with various socio-demographic factors (Arsali, et al., 2008), (Li, et al., 2015). Different components directly or indirectly might influence the betterment of the Service provided.

All of the studies cited in this research have been included and analyzed accordingly. Therefore, this study shall incorporate and allow the integration of socio-demographic variables with a SERVQUAL Model 'main principles components (Parasuraman, et al., 1988).

Generally, in SERVQUAL Model, the following said variables have agreed upon: Age, Sex, Resident Area, Marital Status, Education Background, Profession & Earning

Capacity are addressed (Danasra Dew, et al., 2011) (Arsali, et al., 2008), (Danasra Dew, et al., 2011)

Figure 9: Literature Review Summary

2.4 Literature Summary

Authors	Origin	Purpose	Type of Resources	Research Design	Target Population	Conceptual Framework	Proposed Framework	Major Themes
Parasuraman et al (1988)	USA	Service Quality Assessment	Executive & focused group interview	N/A	Managers & Customers	Yes	Self-Model	Conceptualization, Service Quality, Customer Perception & Expectation
Li et al (2015)	China	Patient 'perception & Service Quality	Questionnaire	N/A	Patients	Yes	No	Conceptualization, Service Quality, Customer Perception & Expectation
Wijenayake et al (2019)	Sri Lanka	Patient 'perception & Service Quality	Questionnaire & Interview	N/A	Patients	Yes	No	Conceptualization, Service Quality, Customer Perception & Expectation
Rengarajan et al (2019)	India	Service Quality Assessment	Questionnaire & Interview	N/A	Customers	Yes	No	Conceptualization, Service Quality, Customer Perception & Expectation
Zun et al (2018)	Malaysia	Patient 'perception & Service Quality	Questionnaire & Interview	N/A	Patients	Yes	No	Conceptualization, Service Quality, Customer Perception & Expectation
Kalaja et al (2016)	Albania	Patient 'perception & Service Quality	Questionnaire	N/A	Patients	Yes	No	Conceptualization, Service Quality, Customer Perception & Expectation
Purcărea et al (2013)	Romania	Patient 'perception & Service Quality	Questionnaire	N/A	Patients	Yes	No	Conceptualization, Service Quality, Customer Perception & Expectation
Mosadeghrad et al (2012)	Iran	Patient 'perception & Service Quality	Questionnaire Executive & focused group interview	N/A	Patients Care providers Managers, Policy makers	Yes	Yes	Conceptualization, Service Quality, Customer Perception & Expectation
Bedman Narteh et al (2017)	Ghana	Customer 'perception & Service Quality	Questionnaire	N/A	Customer	Yes	No	Conceptualization, Service Quality, Customer Perception & Expectation
Kalubowila et al (2017)	Sri Lanka	Patient 'perception & Service Quality	Questionnaire	N/A	Patients	Yes	No	Conceptualization, Service Quality, Customer Perception & Expectation

Table 3.1: Literature Summary

2.5 Literature Mapping

Independent Variables	Sources	
Tangibility	Journal	Kalaja, R., Myshketa, R. & Scalera, F., 2016. Service quality assessment in health care sector: the case of Durres public hospital.
	Journal	Parasuraman, A., Z. V. & B. L., 1988. SERVQUAL: a multiple-item scale for measuring consumer perceptions of service quality
	Journal	Zun, A. B., Ibrahim, M. I. & Hamid, A. A., 2018. Level of Satisfaction on Service Quality Dimensions Based on SERVQUAL Model Among Patients Attending 1 Malaysia Clinic in Kota Bharu, Malaysia.
	Journal	Wijenayake, P., V. K., YJ, S. & MDU, G., 2019. Service quality of psychiatric care from patients'perspective; a descriptive cross sectional study conducted in National Hospital, Sri Lanka
	Journal	Kalubowila, K. C. et al., 2017. Patient satisfaction of services at the out-patient department of Base Hospital Panadura, Sri Lanka
	Journal	Bosompem Boadi, E., Wenxin, W., Bentum-Micah, G. & Jerry Asare, I. K., 2019. Impact of Service Quality on Customer Satisfaction in Ghana hospitals: A PLS-SEM Approach.
	Journal	Zun, A. B., Ibrahim, M. I. & Hamid, A. A., 2018. Level of Satisfaction on Service Quality Dimensions Based on SERVQUAL Model Among Patients Attending 1 Malaysia Clinic in Kota Bharu, Malaysia
	Journal	Punnakitikashem, P., Buavaraporn, N., Maluesri, P. & Leelartapin, K., 2012. <i>Health Care Service Quality</i>
Assurance	Journal	Kalaja, R., Myshketa, R. & Scalera, F., 2016. Service quality assessment in health care sector: the case of Durres public hospital.
	Journal	Kitapci, O., Akdogan, C. & Dortyol, İ. T., 2014. The Impact of Service Quality Dimensions on Patient Satisfaction, Repurchase intentions and Word-of-Mouth Communication in the Public Healthcare Industry
	Journal	Parasuraman, A., Z. V. & B. L., 1988. SERVQUAL: a multiple-item scale for measuring consumer perceptions of service quality.
	Journal	Wijenayake, P., V. K., YJ, S. & MDU, G., 2019. Service quality of psychiatric care from patients'perspective; a descriptive cross sectional study conducted in National Hospital, Sri Lanka
	Journal	Chi, Y. & Quan, Y., 2013. <i>Service Quality Perspective and Customer Satisfaction: Xingya Technical Communication Company</i>
	Journal	Narteh, B., 2017. Service quality and customer satisfaction in Ghanaian retail banks: the moderating role of price.
	Journal	E.T. Jagoda, E.A.K.K. Edirisinghe & M.K.D.L. Meegoda, 2019. <i>Evaluation of Service Quality in Nursing and Patient Satisfaction: Perception of Patients & Student Nurses</i>
	Journal	McCreaddie, M., Benwel, B. & Gritti, A., 2021. A qualitative study of National Health Service (NHS) complaint-responses
Reliability	Journal	Kalaja, R., Myshketa, R. & Scalera, F., 2016. Service quality assessment in health care sector: the case of Durres public hospital.
	Journal	Anbari, Z., Mohammadi, M. & Taheri, M., 2014. Measurement of Quality of Hospital Services via SERVQUAL Model.
	Journal	Bucke, V., Ruzevicius, J. & Buckus, R., 2020. Service Quality Management at Lithuanian Healthcare Institutions
	Journal	Parasuraman, A., Z. V. & B. L., 1988. SERVQUAL: a multiple-item scale for measuring consumer perceptions of service quality.
	Journal	E.T. Jagoda, E.A.K.K. Edirisinghe & M.K.D.L. Meegoda, 2019. <i>Evaluation of Service Quality in Nursing and Patient Satisfaction: Perception of Patients & Student Nurses</i>
	Journal	Wijenayake, P., V. K., YJ, S. & MDU, G., 2019. Service quality of psychiatric care from patients'perspective; a descriptive cross sectional study conducted in National Hospital, Sri Lanka
	Journal	Chi, Y. & Quan, Y., 2013. <i>Service Quality Perspective and Customer Satisfaction: Xingya Technical Communication Company</i>

Table 3.2: Literature Mapping

	Journal	Rengarajan, V., Sangararaman, G., Surulivel, S. & Dinesh, S., 2019. Service Quality Of Airtel Mobile Operator Using Servqual Model In Kanchipuram District, Tamil Nadu
	Journal	Subiyakto, B., Kot, S. & S. S., 2020. The Government Reform on Healthcare Facilities from the Standpoint of Service Quality Performance.
	Journal	Anbari, Z., Mohammadi, M. & Taheri, M., 2014. Measurement of Quality of Hospital Services via SERVQUAL Model
	Journal	Wanninayake , W. M. A. S., Mahakumbura, . M. & Hapugoda, . J. C., 2019. Perceived Service Quality & Customer Loyalty: An Application of SERVQUAL Model in Credits Card segment of Sri Lankan Private sector Banks
Empathy	Journal	Kalaja, R., Myshketa, R. & Scalera, F., 2016. Service quality assessment in health care sector: the case of Durres public hospital.
	Journal	KumarRoy, S., Shekhar, V., M.Lassar, W. & Chen, T., 2018. Customer engagement behaviors: The role of service convenience, fairness and quality.
	Journal	Wijenayake, P., V. K., YJ, S. & MDU, G., 2019. Service quality of psychiatric care from patients'perspective; a descriptive cross sectional study conducted in National Hospital, Sri Lanka
	Journal	Parasuraman, A., Z. V. & B. L., 1988. SERVQUAL: a multiple-item scale for measuring consumer perceptions of service quality.
	Journal	Sadiq Sohail, M., 2003. Service quality in hospitals: more favourable than you think
	Journal	Kalubowila, K. C. et al., 2017. Patient satisfaction of services at the out-patient department of Base Hospital Panadura, Sri Lanka.
	Journal	Gusmano, M. K., Maschke, K. J. & Solomon, M. . Z., 2019. Patient-Centered Care, Yes:Patients As Consumers, No.
	Journal	Sathiyaseelan, T. & Gnanapala, W. K. A. C., 2015. Service Quality and Patients' Satisfaction on Ayurvedic Health Services.
	Journal	Li, M. et al., 2015. Evaluating Patients'perception of service quality at hospitals in nine chinese cities by use of SERVQUAL scale.
Responsiveness	Journal	Kalaja, R., Myshketa, R. & Scalera, F., 2016. Service quality assessment in health care sector: the case of Durres public hospital.
	Journal	Wijenayake, P., V. K., YJ, S. & MDU, G., 2019. Service quality of psychiatric care from patients'perspective; a descriptive cross sectional study conducted in National Hospital, Sri Lanka
	Journal	Sathiyaseelan, T. & Gnanapala, W. K. A. C., 2015. Service Quality and Patients' Satisfaction on Ayurvedic Health Services.
	Journal	Chi, Y. & Quan, Y., 2013. <i>Service Quality Perspective and Customer Satisfaction: Xingya Technical Communication Company</i>
	Journal	Aagia, J. & Garg, R., 2010. Measuring perceived service quality for public hospitals (PubHosQual) in the Indian context.
	Journal	Li, M. et al., 2015. Evaluating Patients'perception of service quality at hospitals in nine chinese cities by use of SERVQUAL scale.
	Journal	Parasuraman, A., Z. V. & B. L., 1988. SERVQUAL: a multiple-item scale for measuring consumer perceptions of service quality.
	Journal	Wijenayake, P., V. K., YJ, S. & MDU, G., 2019. Service quality of psychiatric care from patients'perspective; a descriptive cross sectional study conducted in National Hospital, Sri Lanka
	Journal	Danasra Dew, F., Sudjana, G. & Marty Oesman, Y., 2011. Patient satisfaction analysis on service quality of dental health care based on empathy and responsiveness.

Table 3.3: Literature Mapping

Dependent Variable		Sources
Journal	Journal	Narteh, B., 2017. Service quality and customer satisfaction in Ghanaian retail banks: the moderating role of price.
	Journal	Li, Y. & Shang, H., 2019. Service quality, perceived value, and citizens' continuous-use intention regarding e-government: Empirical evidence from China
	Journal	Mosadeghrad, A. M., 2012. A Conceptual Framework for Quality of Care.
	Journal	Fatima, I., Humayun, A., Iqbal, U. & Shafiq, M., 2019. Dimensions of service quality in healthcare: a systematic review of literature. <i>International Journal for Quality in Health Care</i>
	Journal	Gusmano, M. K., Maschke, K. J. & Solomon, M. . Z., 2019. Patient-Centered Care, Yes: Patients As Consumers, No. <i>Health Affairs</i>
	Book	Kohn, L. T., Corrigan, J. M. & Donaldson, M. S., 2000. Building a Safer Health System. In: <i>to err is human</i> .
	Article	Zun, A. B., Ibrahim, M. I. & Hamid, A. A., 2018. Level of Satisfaction on Service Quality Dimensions Based on SERVQUAL Model Among Patients Attending 1 Malaysia Clinic in Kota Bharu, Malaysia.
	Journal	Parasuraman, A., Z. V. & B. L., 1988. SERVQUAL: a multiple-item scale for measuring consumer perceptions of service quality.
	Journal	Kalaja, R., Myshketa, R. & Scalera, F., 2016. Service quality assessment in health care sector: the case of Durres public hospital.
	Book	Hurtado, M. P., Swift, E. K. & Corrigan., J. M., 2001. <i>Envisioning the National Health Care Quality Report</i> ,
	Journal	Kitapci, O., Akdogan, C. & Dortyol, İ. T., 2014. The Impact of Service Quality Dimensions on Patient Satisfaction, Repurchase intentions and Word-of-Mouth Communication in the Public Healthcare Industry
	Journal	Wijenayake, P., V, K., YJ, S. & MDU, G., 2019. Service quality of psychiatric care from patients' perspective: a descriptive cross sectional study conducted in National Hospital, Sri Lanka
	Journal	Chi, Y. & Quan, Y., 2013. <i>Service Quality Perspective and Customer Satisfaction: Xingya Technical Communication Company</i>
	Journal	Anbari, Z., Mohammadi, M. & Taheri, M., 2014. Measurement of Quality of Hospital Services via SERVQUAL Model.
Journal	KumarRoy, S., Shekhar, V., MLassar, W. & Chen, T., 2018. Customer engagement behaviors: The role of service convenience, fairness and quality.	

Table 3.4: Literature Mapping

3 Chapter Three

3.1 Research Methodology

This chapter represents the more detailed view of the proposed conceptual framework with established & formulated five hypotheses; furthermore, the chapter shall discuss the Operationalization of the research design with specified population, sample size & Data collection & detailed analysis mechanism involved.

3.1.1 Formulated Conceptual Framework of this study

As discussed in the literature reviews & its findings, this research shall propose the following arguments into the feasible framework. It is also stating the IV & DV into argumentative flat form.

Figure 10: Conceptual Model of Hypotheses

3.2 Operational Definitions

3.2.1 Tangibility

In this IV factor, the study shall consider the appearance of the organisation` service premises, including modernised technology, availability of equipment, professional appearance of the staff & appealing nature of the furniture (Kalaja, et al., 2016), (Anbari, et al., 2014), (Geberu, et al., 2019), (Sanjeewa & Senevirathne, 2017), (Rezaei, et al., 2018), (Zun, et al., 2018).

3.2.2 Assurance

This component, as another IV, consists of the following aspects: employees' skills in creating confidence in patients, making them feel that they are in safe hands, employee`s continued dignity maintenance, and knowledge on patient`s queries (Narteh, 2017), (Li, et al., 2015) (Kalubowila, et al., 2017), (Sanjeewa & Senevirathne, 2017).

3.2.3 Reliability

Reliability is important IV in healthcare services; the study shall assess the following aspects under this component such as service as promised, dependability on handling patient`s problem, ability to offer the service in the right manner at first instance, nature of the service on time and proper records maintenance (Sanjeewa & Senevirathne, 2017), (Danasra Dew, et al., 2011), (Purcărea, et al., 2013), (Sohail, 2003), (Kalaja, et al., 2016).

3.2.4 Responsiveness

It is another important IV in Service Quality assessment and essentially includes early information to patients regarding service time, Immediate treatment to patients, helping tendency to patients, nature of answers to patient`s queries with responsibility (Li, et al., 2015), (Wanninayake , et al., 2019), (Wijenayake, et al., 2019).

3.2.5 Empathy

One of the major influential IV components to assess the Service Quality in the SERVQUAL Model, which has included Individual attention to patients, caring nature of the employees, understanding the patient with whole heart, able understand the patient`s need and availability of convenient service time for the patients (E.T. Jagoda, et al., 2019), (Li, et al., 2015).

3.3 Development of Hypothesis

In the Context of Healthcare Service Quality of OPD at DH Palai Killinochchi District, Sri Lanka, Following Hypothesis Formulated,

H10 N (Null): Tangibility has no relationship with Perceived Service Quality H1 A (Alternate): Tangibility has relationship with Perceived Service Quality
H20 N (Null): Assurance has no relationship with Perceived Service Quality H2 A (Alternate): Assurance has relationship with Perceived Service Quality
H30 N (Null): Reliability has no relationship with Perceived Service Quality H3 A (Alternate): Reliability has relationship with Perceived Service Quality
H40 N (Null): Responsiveness has no relationship with Perceived Service Quality H4 A (Alternate): Responsiveness has relationship with Perceived Service Quality
H50 N (Null): Empathy has no relationship with Perceived Service Quality H5 A (Alternate): Empathy has relationship with Perceived Service Quality

3.4 Operationalization

Variable	Indicator	References	Measuring Scale	Question Number
Tangibility	Modern Equipment	Kalubowila, et al., 2017, Bosompem Boadi, et al., 2019, Kalaja, et al., 2016 Wijenayake, et al., 2019, Parasuraman, et al., 1988, Zun, et al., 2018	Likert: (1-5)	Q1
	Appealing Facilities	Zun, et al., 2018, Kalubowila, et al., 2017 Punnakitikashem, et al., 2012, Parasuraman, et al., 1988, Wijenayake, et al., 2019, Kalaja, et al., 2016	Likert: (1-5)	Q2
	Professional Appearance	Sanjeeva & Senevirathne, 2017, Punnakitikashem, et al., 2012, Tantarto, et al., 2020, Parasuraman, et al., 1988, Wijenayake, et al., 2019, Kalaja, et al., 2016, Zun, et al., 2018	Likert: (1-5)	Q3
	Appealing materials	Punnakitikashem, et al., 2012, Bosompem Boadi, et al., 2019, Parasuraman, et al., 1988, Wijenayake, et al., 2019, Kalaja, et al., 2016, Zun, et al., 2018	Likert: (1-5)	Q4
Assurance	Confidence in Patients	Kitapci, et al., 2014, E.T. Jagoda, et al., 201 Bucke, et al., 2020, McCreaddie, et al., 2021, Parasuraman, et al., 1988, Li, et al., 2015, Mahmoud, et al., 2019, Howell, 2012	Likert: (1-5)	Q5
	Comfortability of Patients	Narteh, 2017, Parasuraman, et al., 1988, Kitapci, et al., 2014, E.T. Jagoda, et al., 2019, Li, et al., 2015, McCreaddie, et al., 2021, Howell, 2012, Mahmoud, et al., 2019	Likert: (1-5)	Q6
	Dignified Staff	Narteh, 2017, E.T. Jagoda, et al., 2019, McCreaddie, et al., 2021, Howell, 2012, Bucke, et al., 2020, Parasuraman, et al., 1988, Li, et al., 2015, Mahmoud, et al., 2019	Likert: (1-5)	Q7
	Knowledge on Queries	Kitapci, et al., 2014, Narteh, 2017, Howell, 2012, Bucke, et al., 2020, Parasuraman, et al., 1988, Li, et al., 2015, McCreaddie, et al., 2021, Narteh, 2017	Likert: (1-5)	Q8
Reliability	Promised Service	Bucke, et al., 2020, Sohail, 2003, Parasuraman, et al., 1988, Subiyakto, et al., 2020, Li, et al., 2015, Rengarajan et al, 2019, Jagoda et al, 2019	Likert: (1-5)	Q9
	Ensured Service	Hurtado, et al., 2001, Subiyakto, et al., 2020, Bucke, et al., 2020, Wanninayake, et al., 2019, Anbari, et al., 2014, Sohail, 2003 Parasuraman, et al., 1988, Li, et al., 2015, Rengarajan et al, 2019, Jagoda et al 2019	Likert: (1-5)	Q10
	Initial Right Services	Mosadeghrad, 2012, Anbari, et al., 2014 Sohail, 2003, Bucke, et al., 2020, Parasuraman, et al., 1988, Li, et al., 2015, Rengarajan et al, 2019, Jagoda et al, 2019	Likert: (1-5)	Q11
	Right service on Time	Wanninayake, et al., 2019, Anbari, et al., 2014, Subiyakto, et al., 2020,	Likert: (1-5)	Q12

Table 4.1: Operationalization

		Mosadeghrad, 2012, Bucke, et al., 2020, Hurtado, et al., 2001, Parasuraman, et al., 1988, Li, et al., 2015, Rengarajan et al, 2019, Jagoda et al 2019		
	Accurate Records	Mosadeghrad, 2012, Anbari, et al., 2014, Wanninayake , et al., 2019, Hurtado, et al., 2001, Parasuraman, et al., 1988, Li, et al., 2015, Rengarajan et al 2019, Jagoda et al 2019	Likert: (1-5)	Q13
Responsiveness	Informed Services	Arsali, et al., 2008, Sathiyaseclan & Gnanapala, 2015, Victor Lorin, 2013, Parasuraman, et al., 1988, Wijenayake, et al., 2019	Likert: (1-5)	Q14
	Prompt Services	Wijenayake, et al., 2019, Purcărea, et al., 2013, Mahmoud, et al., 2019, Arsali, et al., 2008, Parasuraman, et al., 1988, Victor Lorin, 2013	Likert: (1-5)	Q15
	Willingness on Help	Mahmoud, et al., 2019, Arsali, et al., 2008 Sathiyaseclan & Gnanapala, 2015, Parasuraman, et al., 1988, Wijenayake, et al., 2019, Victor Lorin, 2013	Likert: (1-5)	Q16
	Preparedness	Sathiyaseclan & Gnanapala, 2015, Mahmoud, et al., 2019, Arsali, et al., 2008 Parasuraman, et al., 1988, Wijenayake, et al., 2019, Victor Lorin, 2013	Likert: (1-5)	Q17
Empathy	Specific Attention	KumarRoy, et al., 2018, Velmurugan, et al., 2019, Fatima, et al., 2019, Parasuraman, et al., 1988, Li, et al., 2015, Danasra Dew, et al., 2011	Likert: (1-5)	Q18
	Caring Fashion	Li & Shang, 2019, Naik, et al., 2013, Fatima, et al., 2019, Velmurugan, et al., 2019, Parasuraman, et al., 1988, Li, et al., 2015, Danasra Dew, et al., 2011	Likert: (1-5)	Q19
	Patient Best Interest	Fatima, et al., 2019, Sathiyaseclan & Gnanapala, 2015, Naik, et al., 2013, Velmurugan, et al., 2019, Parasuraman, et al., 1988, Li, et al., 2015, Danasra Dew, et al., 2011	Likert: (1-5)	Q20
	Understanding Needs	Fatima, et al., 2019, Parasuraman, et al., 1988, Li, et al., 2015, Naik, et al., 2013, Velmurugan, et al., 2019, Danasra Dew, et al., 2011	Likert: (1-5)	Q21
	Service Hours	Sathiyaseclan & Gnanapala, 2015, Fatima, et al., 2019, Naik, et al., 2013, Parasuraman, et al., 1988, Li, et al., 2015, Danasra Dew, et al., 2011	Likert: (1-5)	Q22
Service Quality	Satisfaction	Sathiyaseclan & Gnanapala, 2015	Likert: (1-5)	Q23
	Acceptance	Li & Shang, 2019	Likert: (1-5)	Q24
	Intention want to Return	Li & Shang, 2019	Likert: (1-5)	Q25
	Convenience	KumarRoy, et al., 2018	Likert: (1-5)	Q26
	Complaints	McCreaddie, et al., 2021	Likert: (1-5)	Q27
	Recommend to Others	Kitapci, et al., 2014, Naik, et al., 2013	Likert: (1-5)	Q28

Table 4.2: Operationalization

3.5 Design of Modified SERVQUAL Questionnaire

This research uses the SERVQUAL Model of Parasuraman et al. (1988) to study the OPD Service Quality at Divisional Hospital Palai, Killinochchi District, Sri Lanka. This study shall be a Quantitative method and use the above operationalization component in detail. As part of this questionnaire, it has been formulated to have a basic 22 queries attributed to five dimensions of the SERVQUAL Model and 6 queries attributed for Dependent variable.

Indicators are generated from the Parasuraman et al. (1988) SERVQUAL model accordingly for healthcare service use. The first phase of the questionnaire shall include the Socio-Demographic Variables, which will support the further precision of this study to assess the Service Quality of OPD at DH Palai. The questionnaire shall include the Likert Scalenswer method to choose the best suitable response to assess the Quality Services (Likert, 1932).

3.5.1 Research Design

This is empirical research, following a quantitative approach to test a set of correlation basis hypotheses pertaining to factors affecting healthcare service quality & the perceived service quality of the providers. This is a cross sectional research & which employed a survey questionnaire for the quantitative data for the statistical validation of the hypothesis.

3.5.2 Questionnaire

This shall have two sections. Section one includes information on Socio-Demographic factors, while section two shall include twenty-eight components as closed-ended questions to choose the answer from one to five accordingly & five-point Likert scale.

3.5.3 Research Onion (Appendix 6)

Having a basic model for any study strengthens the research pattern and guides the researcher to develop a successful study (Saunders, et al., 2019). According to this model, the study shall look at least to have six layers, and from each layer, the study includes at least one component.

3.5.4 Research Philosophy: Positivism

According to Saunders et al. (2019), it is mainly considered four main ideologies: Positivism, Pragmatism, Interpretivism & Realism. This study agrees with Positivism since the researcher believes that there is a positive correlation between this study's Independent & Dependent Variables.

3.5.5 The approach of Research: Deductive

It has been proposed to take over as a Deductive study because it is easy to develop the hypothesis involved in this study and agrees with the research philosophy (Saunders, et al., 2019).

3.5.6 Research Strategy: Survey

This study incorporated Survey methodology as prescribed by Saunders, et al (2019). convenient strategy among case study, archival research, experiment, action research, rounded theory, ethnography & narrative inquiry (Saunders, et al., 2019).

3.5.7 Research Choice: Mono method

This study was conducted purely on a single methodology as a questionnaire in which study under quantitative approach rather than mixed/ multi methodology (Saunders, et al., 2019).

3.5.8 Research Time Frame: Cross-Sectional

Compared to Longitudinal Study, this research has used the Cross-Sectional Method to proceed, and hence conditions applied are a single point of time during the data acquiring stage (Saunders, et al., 2019).

3.6 Data Collection Methods: SERVQUAL Questionnaire

According to Saunders (2019), data collection includes Questionnaires, Interviews, mixed types; however, this research shall comply with Questionnaire methods.

3.6.1 Sample Design

Sample selection & design is a crucial factor in any research study; as a fact, this is the representativeness of the study population concerned. It is, however, essential to have a sample design for the defined population, and it plays a vital role in the research outcome. Similarly, it is also essential to consider the time constraint, resources access & other unavoidable limitations (N.Ross, 2005).

According to Sekaran & Bougie (2016), determining sample design is essential to developing proper research.

They further state that feasible research with an adequate sample between 30 to 500 shall give an accurate representation of the studying population enrolled (Sekaran.U & Bougie.R, 2016), therefore representing the population of Pachchilaipalli 14504, at least sample size should be more than 350.

3.6.2 Population

As discussed in the introduction chapter, the Pachchilaipalli population is 14506 in 2021 (Ministry of Home Affairs & Divisional Secretariat Pachchilaipalli, 2021). Therefore, it is reasonable to assume that the study population is 14506 & also assumes that there is no significant migration or Mass movement during the study conducted. Hence, at a given time, the population shall access the OPD Services at DH Palai.

3.6.3 Sample selection Procedure

Many methodologies are applied while selecting the sampling procedure & according to the requirement of the research conducted. This study shall perform under simple random sampling, where probability & non-probability sampling is used with random sample and convenience sampling. Further, whoever seeks OPD Services is assumed as a random sample of the study population.

3.6.4 Sample Size

The sample size is significant for any research. This study was conducted using the Morgan `sample calculation tool and established with 95 % Confidence Level (CL), whereas Confidence Interval (CI) shall be 5%. The required sample size for this research was calculated accordingly as 374, illustrated below.

Determine Sample Size

Confidence Level: 95% 99%

Confidence Interval:

Population:

Sample size needed:

Figure11: Calculated Sample Size (The Survey System, 2022)

3.7 Data Collection Method

One of the crucial parts of the study is data collection and massive, devoted time spent on this primary data collection by using the Questionnaire as discussed above. Secondary data associated & quoted in this research are derived from the Hospital Statistics of DH Palai, Annual Health Bulletin, Annual Statistics of Provincial Office, RDHS Office, Minutes, Ministry of Health Publications, and Divisional Secretariat Pachchilaipalli & Killinochchi.

Primarily, the Questionnaire consists of Section One with ten queries for general information & Section two has 22 queries for Five Independent Variables (IV) and one Dependent Variable with 6 queries. Answers have been provided with the 5-point scale of Likert 'scale.

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
1	2	3	4	5

Table 5: Five Point Likert`s scale for Questionnaire (Bounthavong, 2019)

This questionnaire was pretested with 20 patients at OPD Premises of DH Palai to assess the functional usage of easy understanding & readability of the content and confirmed that the questionnaire was easy to understand and able to readable. Questionnaire was initially printed in English and since most of the samples are from the Tamil speaking community, therefore translated officially into Tamil by the Official Translator of DH Palai. Questionnaires were in Tamil (374) and in English (26), altogether 400 samples were collected & 2 were rejected due to incomplete responses, finally 398 samples used for the statistical analysis.

3.8 Research Data Analysis Techniques

IBM SPSS Version -26 software used for Statistical Analysis. The Cronbach`s Alpha was applied to check the reliability of the prepared questionnaire of this study from the selected random sample. Preferably Pearson`s correlation used to study the variables and Multiple Regression Analysis used to test the validity of the Hypothesis.

4 Chapter Four

4.1 Introduction to Statistical Analysis

4.1.1 The Data Interpretation & Presentation

4.1.1.1 Brief

This chapter shall discuss the analysis of data and presentation of such meaningful information related to this research. This study primarily focuses on answers for the hypothesis formulated and finds the solutions for the research objective of this study. As discussed, chapter three, data was collected using five-point Likert scale questionnaires, which was used at OPD of DH Palai. Since the population was targeted as 14504 (Current Population of Pachchilaipalli) and sample size calculated as 374 based on Morgan's sample calculator. It managed to collect 398 samples which is more than 100% response rate and all of them used since there is no significance when it considers the larger population like more than 14500 or unknown larger population.

4.1.2 Analysis of Socio Demographic Data of Respondents

Sample of this study was selected based on various socio demographic factors of respondents after the detailed literature reviews and selected as Age Groups, Gender, Education, Employment, Marital Status, Number of Children, Area of Living, Monthly Income, Work Experiences, Number of OPD Visits and carefully used hence researcher considered that demographic variables can have different perception of Healthcare Service Quality of the OPD Services of DH Palai.

4.1.2.1 Gender

Figure 12: Gender (SPSS version26)

Figure 12 describes that Female gender were majority patients (64.82%) responses and minority were male patients (35.18%). It is very interesting that the majority of them are female patients or mothers with children.

4.1.2.2 Age Group

Figure 13: Age Group (SPSS version26)

Figure 13 illustrates that, Variable age has divided into six categories, where most of the participants (31.7%) fall into 36-50 while few (0.75%) of them are less than 18. Other age groups were also responded significantly such as 26-35 (26.63%) and 51-65 (17.34%). This depicts that all the age groups of patients using the OPD were involved in the responses.

4.1.2.3 Marital Status

Figure 14: Marital Status (SPSS version26)

Figure 14 shows that the majority of them were married (73.87%) and significantly 17.59 % which is under the category of Single (Unmarried) also use the OPD services and responded.

4.1.2.4 Education

Figure 15: Education (SPSS version26)

Most of the respondents in this variable attended only School (77.14%) and least were Undergraduate Degree holders representing 6.78%.

4.1.2.5 Area of Living

Figure 16: Area of Living (SPSS version26)

Figure 16 indicates that most of the respondents were from rural areas (84.67%) and around 15.33% from Urban areas.

4.1.2.6 Employment

Figure 17: Employment (SPSS version26)

Figure 17 illustrates that 32.16% are full time employed respondents and significantly 15.83% are unemployed. This indicates all the groups of employment background were involved in the sample responses.

4.1.2.7 Number of Children

Figure 18: Number of Children (SPSS version26)

Figure 18 illustrates that Among respondents around 40.70% are with 1-2 children, least are 3.27% with children more than 6. This indicates that a different number of family members grouped have participated in the study.

4.1.2.8 Duration of Works

Figure 19: Duration of Works (SPSS version26)

Figure 19 depicts that patient who have respondents for the questionnaire around 42.48% have no working experiences and least are 4.27% representing the working experiences greater than 30 years. This illustrates that participants were from different employment groups.

4.1.2.9 Number of Visits to OPD

Figure 20: Number of OPD Visits (SPSS version26)

Figure 20 represents that 72.11 % respondents were have visited OPD of DH Palai, whereas 4.02% have visited at least once. This indicates that respondents were from different experience groups for the OPD Visits.

4.1.2.10 Monthly Income

Figure 21: Income (SPSS version26)

Figure 21 illustrates that around 60.30% respondents are earning less than 25000.00 Sri Lankan Rupees per month. Respondents earning more than 300,000.00 Rs are around 0.75%. which illustrates that different earning capacity respondents participated in the study.

4.2 The Reliability Test of the gathered Data

Cronbach's Alpha can be applied to measure the internal consistency of the components integrated in the questionnaire, that is, how closely related set items are as a group. It is considered to be a measure of scale reliability.

Independent Variable				Independent Variable			
Scale: Tangibility				Scale: Assurance			
Case Processing Summary				Case Processing Summary			
		N	%			N	%
Cases	Valid	398	100.0	Cases	Valid	398	100.0
	Excluded ^a	0	.0		Excluded ^a	0	.0
	Total	398	100.0		Total	398	100.0
a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.				a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.			
Reliability Statistics				Reliability Statistics			
		Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items			Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
Cronbach's Alpha		.849	4	Cronbach's Alpha		.890	4
Scale: Reliability				Scale: Responsiveness			
Case Processing Summary				Case Processing Summary			
		N	%			N	%
Cases	Valid	398	100.0	Cases	Valid	398	100.0
	Excluded ^a	0	.0		Excluded ^a	0	.0
	Total	398	100.0		Total	398	100.0
a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.				a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.			
Reliability Statistics				Reliability Statistics			
		Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items			Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
Cronbach's Alpha		.874	5	Cronbach's Alpha		.891	4

Table 6.1: Reliability of Variables (SPSS version26)

Scale: Empathy				Dependent Variable			
				Scale: Service Quality			
Case Processing Summary				Case Processing Summary			
		N	%			N	%
Cases	Valid	398	100.0	Cases	Valid	398	100.0
	Excluded ^a	0	.0		Excluded ^a	0	.0
	Total	398	100.0		Total	398	100.0
a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.				a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.			
Reliability Statistics				Reliability Statistics			
		Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items			Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
Cronbach's Alpha		.902	5	Cronbach's Alpha		.898	6

Table 6.2: Reliability of Variables (SPSS version26)

Alpha Coefficient Range	Strength of Association
Less than 0.6	Poor
0.6 to < 0.7	Moderate
0.7 to < 0.8	Good
0.8 to < 0.9	Very Good
0.9 and above	Excellent

Table 7: The Thumb rule for Cronbach’s Alpha value (Hair, J, et al., 2016), (Sekaran.U & Bougie.R, 2016)

Thumb rule described by Hair.J et al. (2016) & Uma Sekaran (2016) states that, value < 0.6 is a poor, between the range of 0.6 and 0.7 is a moderate level and > 0.8 is a high-level reliability. This research, all the given variables have very good reliability.

Variables	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted	Number of Questions	Reliability
Tangibility	0.846	4	Very Good
Assurance	0.890	4	Very Good
Reliability	0.874	5	Very Good
Responsiveness	0.891	4	Very Good
Empathy	0.902	5	Excellent
Service Quality	0.898	6	Very Good

Table 8: The Cronbach's Alpha for each given variable (SPSS version26)

→ Reliability

Scale: ALL VARIABLES

Case Processing Summary

		N	%
Cases	Valid	398	100.0
	Excluded ^a	0	.0
	Total	398	100.0

a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.895	6

Table 9: The Scale of All Variables (SPSS version26)

Therefore, the Cronbach's Alpha coefficient constructed for all the Likert scale items in the questionnaire is 0.895, suggesting that these items have relatively high internal consistency.

4.3 Descriptive Statistics Analysis of Collected Data

This section describes the detailed descriptive statistics of each variable how given respondent rated the research questionnaire of this study and illustrates including pattern of data that is distributed and spread (Kurtosis test & Skewness)

		Statistics					
		Tangibility	Assurance	Reliability	Responsiveness	Empathy	Service Quality
N	Valid	398	398	398	398	398	398
	Missing	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mean		3.5879	3.7889	3.6608	3.6985	3.6407	3.7261
Std. Error of Mean		.04601	.03996	.04050	.04583	.04222	.04081
Median		4.0000	4.0000	4.0000	4.0000	4.0000	4.0000
Mode		4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00
Std. Deviation		.91781	.79715	.80803	.91423	.84224	.81415
Variance		.842	.635	.653	.836	.709	.663
Skewness		-.369	-.293	-.402	-.480	-.386	-.331
Std. Error of Skewness		.122	.122	.122	.122	.122	.122
Kurtosis		-.010	-.158	.332	.085	.339	.114
Std. Error of Kurtosis		.244	.244	.244	.244	.244	.244
Range		4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00
Minimum		1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Maximum		5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00
Sum		1428.00	1508.00	1457.00	1472.00	1449.00	1483.00
Percentiles	25	3.0000	3.0000	3.0000	3.0000	3.0000	3.0000
	50	4.0000	4.0000	4.0000	4.0000	4.0000	4.0000
	75	4.0000	4.0000	4.0000	4.0000	4.0000	4.0000

Table 10: Statistics of Descriptive Variable (SPSS version26)

Table 10 illustrates the mean statistics of sample shows 3.5879 as Tangibility, 3.7889 for Assurance, 3.6608 for Reliability, 3.6985 for Responsiveness, 3.6407 for Empathy & 3.7261 for Service Quality. That indicates most of the participants are rated from neither agree or nor disagree to Strongly Disagree. Greater the values for Standard Deviation of all the variables indicates that the data set is dispersed over a wide range.

4.3.1 Skewness

	N Statistic	Skewness		Kurtosis	
		Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Std. Error
Tangibility	398	-.369	.122	-.010	.244
Assurance	398	-.293	.122	-.158	.244
Reliability	398	-.402	.122	.332	.244
Responsiveness	398	-.480	.122	.085	.244
Empathy	398	-.386	.122	.339	.244
Service_Quality	398	-.331	.122	.114	.244
Valid N (listwise)	398				

Table 11: The Descriptive statistics of Skewness & Kurtosis (SPSS version26)

According to Hair (2017), When the Skewness is Zero (Hair, et al., 2017), responses are considered as Normal Distribution. This research as illustrated in the Table, the Skewness for Tangibility (-0.369), Assurance (-0.293), Reliability (-0.402), Responsiveness (-0.480), Empathy (-0.386) & for Service Quality (-0.331). In SPSS, if Skewness is less than ± 1.0 to be considered normal (Orcan, 2020). Therefore, Skewness of this study is less than ± 1.0 & formed between the range of -0.5 and 0.5 that indicates the set data spread is fairly distributed as symmetrical.

Value for Skewness	Nature of Data Distribution
Between -0.5 and 0.5	Fairly Symmetrical
Between -1 and -0.5	Negative & Moderately Skewed
Between + 0.5 and 1	Positive and Moderately Skewed
Less than -1	Negative and Highly Skewed
Greater +1	Positive and Highly Skewed

Table12: Skewness Rule (Hair, et al., 2017) (Sekaran.U & Bougie.R, 2016)

4.3.2 The Kurtosis Test of this research

Orcan (2020) states that for the SPSS, if the Kurtosis is Less than ± 1.0 to be considered normal. In this study, Kurtosis for Tangibility (-0.010), Assurance (-0.158), Reliability (0.332), Responsiveness (0.085), Empathy (0.339) & for Service Quality (0.114), describes that distribution is light tailed (Orcan, 2020), (Westfall, et al., 2017), (Sekaran.U & Bougie.R, 2016).

4.4 Multicollinearity Test

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	R Square Change	Change Statistics			Sig. F Change	Durbin-Watson
						F Change	df1	df2		
1	.745 ^a	.556	.550	.54615	.556	98.041	5	392	<.001	1.897

a. Predictors: (Constant), Empathy, Tangibility, Reliability, Assurance, Responsiveness

b. Dependent Variable: Service Quality

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B		Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error				Lower Bound	Upper Bound	Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	.656	.149		4.410	<.001	.364	.949		
	Tangibility	.099	.038	.111	2.608	.009	.024	.173	.620	1.612
	Assurance	.024	.051	.023	.471	.638	-.076	.123	.463	2.162
	Reliability	.242	.051	.240	4.718	<.001	.141	.343	.438	2.283
	Responsiveness	.100	.048	.113	2.091	.037	.006	.195	.391	2.560
	Empathy	.376	.051	.389	7.400	<.001	.276	.476	.410	2.437

a. Dependent Variable: Service Quality

Table 13: The Variance Inflation Factors (VIF) of Each Variable of this Study (SPSS version26)

based on Seneviratne & Cooray (2019), claims that if VIF is greater than 2.5 is need to be concern and as a rule of thumb of Multicollinearity is a crucial problem when VIF_k is greater than 4 and, if VIK is greater than 10 then it is a vital problem. The output above shows a VIF of all the independent variables are less than 2.5 except Responsiveness which is 2.560, still the model shows that data set redundancy of this study is low between the given variables. Further, Durbin Watson of this study is 1.897, which is less than 2 indicates that there is no autocorrelation identified in the sample.

4.5 Frequency Table for Questionnaire `s Responses

No	Questions						
Tangibility							
1	Using Modern Equipment; (Digital Thermometer, Pulse Oximeter ECG, X-ray Machine, Scan. Ambulance)	Tangibility_Q1					
				Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
		Valid	Strongly Disagree	63	15.8	15.8	15.8
			Disagree	58	14.6	14.6	30.4
			Neutral	144	36.2	36.2	66.6
			Agree	87	21.9	21.9	88.4
			Strongly Agree	46	11.6	11.6	100.0
			Agree				
			Total	398	100.0	100.0	
2	Visually appealing Facilities (Fever Triage, Reception, Seating, Hand washing, rest room, rooms for feeding mothers)	Tangibility_Q2					
				Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
		Valid	Strongly Disagree	21	5.3	5.3	5.3
			Disagree	68	17.1	17.1	22.4
			Neutral	143	35.9	35.9	58.3
			Agree	111	27.9	27.9	86.2
			Strongly Agree	55	13.8	13.8	100.0
			Agree				
			Total	398	100.0	100.0	
3	Employees, who have a neat, Professional appearance (Uniform, wearing shoes with socks, wearing mask)	Tangibility_Q3					
				Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
		Valid	Strongly Disagree	11	2.8	2.8	2.8
			Disagree	31	7.8	7.8	10.6
			Neutral	115	28.9	28.9	39.4
			Agree	133	33.4	33.4	72.9
			Strongly Agree	108	27.1	27.1	100.0
			Agree				
			Total	398	100.0	100.0	

Table 14.1: Frequency Responses of all the Variables (SPSS version26)

4	<p>Visually appealing materials associated with service (Instruction, direction, health banners, Name boards, Computers)</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Tangibility_Q4</p> <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <thead> <tr> <th colspan="2"></th> <th>Frequency</th> <th>Percent</th> <th>Valid Percent</th> <th>Cumulative Percent</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Valid</td> <td>Strongly Disagree</td> <td>11</td> <td>2.8</td> <td>2.8</td> <td>2.8</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Disagree</td> <td>31</td> <td>7.8</td> <td>7.8</td> <td>10.6</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Neutral</td> <td>95</td> <td>23.9</td> <td>23.9</td> <td>34.4</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Agree</td> <td>148</td> <td>37.2</td> <td>37.2</td> <td>71.6</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Strongly Agree</td> <td>113</td> <td>28.4</td> <td>28.4</td> <td>100.0</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Total</td> <td>398</td> <td>100.0</td> <td>100.0</td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>			Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent	Valid	Strongly Disagree	11	2.8	2.8	2.8		Disagree	31	7.8	7.8	10.6		Neutral	95	23.9	23.9	34.4		Agree	148	37.2	37.2	71.6		Strongly Agree	113	28.4	28.4	100.0		Total	398	100.0	100.0	
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent																																							
Valid	Strongly Disagree	11	2.8	2.8	2.8																																							
	Disagree	31	7.8	7.8	10.6																																							
	Neutral	95	23.9	23.9	34.4																																							
	Agree	148	37.2	37.2	71.6																																							
	Strongly Agree	113	28.4	28.4	100.0																																							
	Total	398	100.0	100.0																																								
Assurance																																												
5	<p>Employees who instill confidence in patients (Be confidential)</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Assurance_Q5</p> <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <thead> <tr> <th colspan="2"></th> <th>Frequency</th> <th>Percent</th> <th>Valid Percent</th> <th>Cumulative Percent</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Valid</td> <td>Strongly Disagree</td> <td>8</td> <td>2.0</td> <td>2.0</td> <td>2.0</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Disagree</td> <td>26</td> <td>6.5</td> <td>6.5</td> <td>8.5</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Neutral</td> <td>127</td> <td>31.9</td> <td>31.9</td> <td>40.5</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Agree</td> <td>162</td> <td>40.7</td> <td>40.7</td> <td>81.2</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Strongly Agree</td> <td>75</td> <td>18.8</td> <td>18.8</td> <td>100.0</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Total</td> <td>398</td> <td>100.0</td> <td>100.0</td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>			Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent	Valid	Strongly Disagree	8	2.0	2.0	2.0		Disagree	26	6.5	6.5	8.5		Neutral	127	31.9	31.9	40.5		Agree	162	40.7	40.7	81.2		Strongly Agree	75	18.8	18.8	100.0		Total	398	100.0	100.0	
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent																																							
Valid	Strongly Disagree	8	2.0	2.0	2.0																																							
	Disagree	26	6.5	6.5	8.5																																							
	Neutral	127	31.9	31.9	40.5																																							
	Agree	162	40.7	40.7	81.2																																							
	Strongly Agree	75	18.8	18.8	100.0																																							
	Total	398	100.0	100.0																																								
6	<p>Making patients feel safe in their transactions (assure safety & security)</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Assurance_Q6</p> <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <thead> <tr> <th colspan="2"></th> <th>Frequency</th> <th>Percent</th> <th>Valid Percent</th> <th>Cumulative Percent</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Valid</td> <td>Strongly Disagree</td> <td>7</td> <td>1.8</td> <td>1.8</td> <td>1.8</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Disagree</td> <td>28</td> <td>7.0</td> <td>7.0</td> <td>8.8</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Neutral</td> <td>146</td> <td>36.7</td> <td>36.7</td> <td>45.5</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Agree</td> <td>146</td> <td>36.7</td> <td>36.7</td> <td>82.2</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Strongly Agree</td> <td>71</td> <td>17.8</td> <td>17.8</td> <td>100.0</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Total</td> <td>398</td> <td>100.0</td> <td>100.0</td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>			Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent	Valid	Strongly Disagree	7	1.8	1.8	1.8		Disagree	28	7.0	7.0	8.8		Neutral	146	36.7	36.7	45.5		Agree	146	36.7	36.7	82.2		Strongly Agree	71	17.8	17.8	100.0		Total	398	100.0	100.0	
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent																																							
Valid	Strongly Disagree	7	1.8	1.8	1.8																																							
	Disagree	28	7.0	7.0	8.8																																							
	Neutral	146	36.7	36.7	45.5																																							
	Agree	146	36.7	36.7	82.2																																							
	Strongly Agree	71	17.8	17.8	100.0																																							
	Total	398	100.0	100.0																																								

Table 14.2: Frequency Responses of all the Variables (SPSS version26)

7	<p>Employees who are consistently courteous (have respect & be credible)</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Assurance_Q7</p> <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <thead> <tr> <th colspan="2"></th> <th>Frequency</th> <th>Percent</th> <th>Valid Percent</th> <th>Cumulative Percent</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td rowspan="6" style="text-align: center;">Valid</td> <td style="text-align: center;">Strongly Disagree</td> <td style="text-align: center;">3</td> <td style="text-align: center;">.8</td> <td style="text-align: center;">.8</td> <td style="text-align: center;">.8</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;">Disagree</td> <td style="text-align: center;">42</td> <td style="text-align: center;">10.6</td> <td style="text-align: center;">10.6</td> <td style="text-align: center;">11.3</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;">Neutral</td> <td style="text-align: center;">118</td> <td style="text-align: center;">29.6</td> <td style="text-align: center;">29.6</td> <td style="text-align: center;">41.0</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;">Agree</td> <td style="text-align: center;">167</td> <td style="text-align: center;">42.0</td> <td style="text-align: center;">42.0</td> <td style="text-align: center;">82.9</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;">Strongly Agree</td> <td style="text-align: center;">68</td> <td style="text-align: center;">17.1</td> <td style="text-align: center;">17.1</td> <td style="text-align: center;">100.0</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;">Total</td> <td style="text-align: center;">398</td> <td style="text-align: center;">100.0</td> <td style="text-align: center;">100.0</td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>			Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent	Valid	Strongly Disagree	3	.8	.8	.8	Disagree	42	10.6	10.6	11.3	Neutral	118	29.6	29.6	41.0	Agree	167	42.0	42.0	82.9	Strongly Agree	68	17.1	17.1	100.0	Total	398	100.0	100.0	
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent																																		
Valid	Strongly Disagree	3	.8	.8	.8																																		
	Disagree	42	10.6	10.6	11.3																																		
	Neutral	118	29.6	29.6	41.0																																		
	Agree	167	42.0	42.0	82.9																																		
	Strongly Agree	68	17.1	17.1	100.0																																		
	Total	398	100.0	100.0																																			
8	<p>Employees who have the knowledge to answer patients' questions (Be competent)</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Assurance_Q8</p> <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <thead> <tr> <th colspan="2"></th> <th>Frequency</th> <th>Percent</th> <th>Valid Percent</th> <th>Cumulative Percent</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td rowspan="6" style="text-align: center;">Valid</td> <td style="text-align: center;">Strongly Disagree</td> <td style="text-align: center;">6</td> <td style="text-align: center;">1.5</td> <td style="text-align: center;">1.5</td> <td style="text-align: center;">1.5</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;">Disagree</td> <td style="text-align: center;">35</td> <td style="text-align: center;">8.8</td> <td style="text-align: center;">8.8</td> <td style="text-align: center;">10.3</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;">Neutral</td> <td style="text-align: center;">116</td> <td style="text-align: center;">29.1</td> <td style="text-align: center;">29.1</td> <td style="text-align: center;">39.4</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;">Agree</td> <td style="text-align: center;">166</td> <td style="text-align: center;">41.7</td> <td style="text-align: center;">41.7</td> <td style="text-align: center;">81.2</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;">Strongly Agree</td> <td style="text-align: center;">75</td> <td style="text-align: center;">18.8</td> <td style="text-align: center;">18.8</td> <td style="text-align: center;">100.0</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;">Total</td> <td style="text-align: center;">398</td> <td style="text-align: center;">100.0</td> <td style="text-align: center;">100.0</td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>			Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent	Valid	Strongly Disagree	6	1.5	1.5	1.5	Disagree	35	8.8	8.8	10.3	Neutral	116	29.1	29.1	39.4	Agree	166	41.7	41.7	81.2	Strongly Agree	75	18.8	18.8	100.0	Total	398	100.0	100.0	
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent																																		
Valid	Strongly Disagree	6	1.5	1.5	1.5																																		
	Disagree	35	8.8	8.8	10.3																																		
	Neutral	116	29.1	29.1	39.4																																		
	Agree	166	41.7	41.7	81.2																																		
	Strongly Agree	75	18.8	18.8	100.0																																		
	Total	398	100.0	100.0																																			
Reliability																																							
9	<p>Providing service as promised (Timeliness)</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Reliability_Q9</p> <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <thead> <tr> <th colspan="2"></th> <th>Frequency</th> <th>Percent</th> <th>Valid Percent</th> <th>Cumulative Percent</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td rowspan="6" style="text-align: center;">Valid</td> <td style="text-align: center;">Strongly Disagree</td> <td style="text-align: center;">5</td> <td style="text-align: center;">1.3</td> <td style="text-align: center;">1.3</td> <td style="text-align: center;">1.3</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;">Disagree</td> <td style="text-align: center;">30</td> <td style="text-align: center;">7.5</td> <td style="text-align: center;">7.5</td> <td style="text-align: center;">8.8</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;">Neutral</td> <td style="text-align: center;">123</td> <td style="text-align: center;">30.9</td> <td style="text-align: center;">30.9</td> <td style="text-align: center;">39.7</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;">Agree</td> <td style="text-align: center;">168</td> <td style="text-align: center;">42.2</td> <td style="text-align: center;">42.2</td> <td style="text-align: center;">81.9</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;">Strongly Agree</td> <td style="text-align: center;">72</td> <td style="text-align: center;">18.1</td> <td style="text-align: center;">18.1</td> <td style="text-align: center;">100.0</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;">Total</td> <td style="text-align: center;">398</td> <td style="text-align: center;">100.0</td> <td style="text-align: center;">100.0</td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>			Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent	Valid	Strongly Disagree	5	1.3	1.3	1.3	Disagree	30	7.5	7.5	8.8	Neutral	123	30.9	30.9	39.7	Agree	168	42.2	42.2	81.9	Strongly Agree	72	18.1	18.1	100.0	Total	398	100.0	100.0	
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent																																		
Valid	Strongly Disagree	5	1.3	1.3	1.3																																		
	Disagree	30	7.5	7.5	8.8																																		
	Neutral	123	30.9	30.9	39.7																																		
	Agree	168	42.2	42.2	81.9																																		
	Strongly Agree	72	18.1	18.1	100.0																																		
	Total	398	100.0	100.0																																			

Table 14.3: Frequency Responses of all the Variables (SPSS version26)

10	Dependability in handling patients' service problems (consistency)	<p style="text-align: center;">Reliability_Q10</p> <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <thead> <tr> <th colspan="2"></th> <th>Frequency</th> <th>Percent</th> <th>Valid Percent</th> <th>Cumulative Percent</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Valid</td> <td>Strongly Disagree</td> <td>8</td> <td>2.0</td> <td>2.0</td> <td>2.0</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Disagree</td> <td>40</td> <td>10.1</td> <td>10.1</td> <td>12.1</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Neutral</td> <td>123</td> <td>30.9</td> <td>30.9</td> <td>43.0</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Agree</td> <td>171</td> <td>43.0</td> <td>43.0</td> <td>85.9</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Strongly Agree</td> <td>56</td> <td>14.1</td> <td>14.1</td> <td>100.0</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Total</td> <td>398</td> <td>100.0</td> <td>100.0</td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>							Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent	Valid	Strongly Disagree	8	2.0	2.0	2.0		Disagree	40	10.1	10.1	12.1		Neutral	123	30.9	30.9	43.0		Agree	171	43.0	43.0	85.9		Strongly Agree	56	14.1	14.1	100.0		Total	398	100.0	100.0	
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent																																											
Valid	Strongly Disagree	8	2.0	2.0	2.0																																											
	Disagree	40	10.1	10.1	12.1																																											
	Neutral	123	30.9	30.9	43.0																																											
	Agree	171	43.0	43.0	85.9																																											
	Strongly Agree	56	14.1	14.1	100.0																																											
	Total	398	100.0	100.0																																												
11	Performing services right the first time	<p style="text-align: center;">Reliability_Q11</p> <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <thead> <tr> <th colspan="2"></th> <th>Frequency</th> <th>Percent</th> <th>Valid Percent</th> <th>Cumulative Percent</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Valid</td> <td>Strongly Disagree</td> <td>5</td> <td>1.3</td> <td>1.3</td> <td>1.3</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Disagree</td> <td>35</td> <td>8.8</td> <td>8.8</td> <td>10.1</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Neutral</td> <td>135</td> <td>33.9</td> <td>33.9</td> <td>44.0</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Agree</td> <td>158</td> <td>39.7</td> <td>39.7</td> <td>83.7</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Strongly Agree</td> <td>65</td> <td>16.3</td> <td>16.3</td> <td>100.0</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Total</td> <td>398</td> <td>100.0</td> <td>100.0</td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>							Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent	Valid	Strongly Disagree	5	1.3	1.3	1.3		Disagree	35	8.8	8.8	10.1		Neutral	135	33.9	33.9	44.0		Agree	158	39.7	39.7	83.7		Strongly Agree	65	16.3	16.3	100.0		Total	398	100.0	100.0	
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent																																											
Valid	Strongly Disagree	5	1.3	1.3	1.3																																											
	Disagree	35	8.8	8.8	10.1																																											
	Neutral	135	33.9	33.9	44.0																																											
	Agree	158	39.7	39.7	83.7																																											
	Strongly Agree	65	16.3	16.3	100.0																																											
	Total	398	100.0	100.0																																												
12	Performing services as the promised time (Regularity)	<p style="text-align: center;">Reliability_Q12</p> <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <thead> <tr> <th colspan="2"></th> <th>Frequency</th> <th>Percent</th> <th>Valid Percent</th> <th>Cumulative Percent</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Valid</td> <td>Strongly Disagree</td> <td>10</td> <td>2.5</td> <td>2.5</td> <td>2.5</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Disagree</td> <td>35</td> <td>8.8</td> <td>8.8</td> <td>11.3</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Neutral</td> <td>116</td> <td>29.1</td> <td>29.1</td> <td>40.5</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Agree</td> <td>171</td> <td>43.0</td> <td>43.0</td> <td>83.4</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Strongly Agree</td> <td>66</td> <td>16.6</td> <td>16.6</td> <td>100.0</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Total</td> <td>398</td> <td>100.0</td> <td>100.0</td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>							Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent	Valid	Strongly Disagree	10	2.5	2.5	2.5		Disagree	35	8.8	8.8	11.3		Neutral	116	29.1	29.1	40.5		Agree	171	43.0	43.0	83.4		Strongly Agree	66	16.6	16.6	100.0		Total	398	100.0	100.0	
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent																																											
Valid	Strongly Disagree	10	2.5	2.5	2.5																																											
	Disagree	35	8.8	8.8	11.3																																											
	Neutral	116	29.1	29.1	40.5																																											
	Agree	171	43.0	43.0	83.4																																											
	Strongly Agree	66	16.6	16.6	100.0																																											
	Total	398	100.0	100.0																																												

Table 14.4: Frequency Responses of all the Variables (SPSS version26)

13	Maintaining error- free records (Accuracy)	<p style="text-align: center;">Reliability_Q13</p> <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <thead> <tr> <th colspan="2"></th> <th>Frequency</th> <th>Percent</th> <th>Valid Percent</th> <th>Cumulative Percent</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Valid</td> <td>Strongly Disagree</td> <td>8</td> <td>2.0</td> <td>2.0</td> <td>2.0</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Disagree</td> <td>27</td> <td>6.8</td> <td>6.8</td> <td>8.8</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Neutral</td> <td>118</td> <td>29.6</td> <td>29.6</td> <td>38.4</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Agree</td> <td>156</td> <td>39.2</td> <td>39.2</td> <td>77.6</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Strongly Agree</td> <td>89</td> <td>22.4</td> <td>22.4</td> <td>100.0</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Total</td> <td>398</td> <td>100.0</td> <td>100.0</td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>							Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent	Valid	Strongly Disagree	8	2.0	2.0	2.0		Disagree	27	6.8	6.8	8.8		Neutral	118	29.6	29.6	38.4		Agree	156	39.2	39.2	77.6		Strongly Agree	89	22.4	22.4	100.0		Total	398	100.0	100.0	
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent																																											
Valid	Strongly Disagree	8	2.0	2.0	2.0																																											
	Disagree	27	6.8	6.8	8.8																																											
	Neutral	118	29.6	29.6	38.4																																											
	Agree	156	39.2	39.2	77.6																																											
	Strongly Agree	89	22.4	22.4	100.0																																											
	Total	398	100.0	100.0																																												
Responsiveness																																																
14	Keeping patients informed about when services will be performed (Doctors routines, cancellation of OPD service, health staff Strikes, Problem Solving)	<p style="text-align: center;">Responsiveness_Q14</p> <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <thead> <tr> <th colspan="2"></th> <th>Frequency</th> <th>Percent</th> <th>Valid Percent</th> <th>Cumulative Percent</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Valid</td> <td>Strongly Disagree</td> <td>27</td> <td>6.8</td> <td>6.8</td> <td>6.8</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Disagree</td> <td>46</td> <td>11.6</td> <td>11.6</td> <td>18.3</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Neutral</td> <td>130</td> <td>32.7</td> <td>32.7</td> <td>51.0</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Agree</td> <td>134</td> <td>33.7</td> <td>33.7</td> <td>84.7</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Strongly Agree</td> <td>61</td> <td>15.3</td> <td>15.3</td> <td>100.0</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Total</td> <td>398</td> <td>100.0</td> <td>100.0</td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>							Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent	Valid	Strongly Disagree	27	6.8	6.8	6.8		Disagree	46	11.6	11.6	18.3		Neutral	130	32.7	32.7	51.0		Agree	134	33.7	33.7	84.7		Strongly Agree	61	15.3	15.3	100.0		Total	398	100.0	100.0	
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent																																											
Valid	Strongly Disagree	27	6.8	6.8	6.8																																											
	Disagree	46	11.6	11.6	18.3																																											
	Neutral	130	32.7	32.7	51.0																																											
	Agree	134	33.7	33.7	84.7																																											
	Strongly Agree	61	15.3	15.3	100.0																																											
	Total	398	100.0	100.0																																												
15	Prompt service to patients	<p style="text-align: center;">Responsiveness_Q15</p> <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <thead> <tr> <th colspan="2"></th> <th>Frequency</th> <th>Percent</th> <th>Valid Percent</th> <th>Cumulative Percent</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Valid</td> <td>Strongly Disagree</td> <td>13</td> <td>3.3</td> <td>3.3</td> <td>3.3</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Disagree</td> <td>48</td> <td>12.1</td> <td>12.1</td> <td>15.3</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Neutral</td> <td>116</td> <td>29.1</td> <td>29.1</td> <td>44.5</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Agree</td> <td>140</td> <td>35.2</td> <td>35.2</td> <td>79.6</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Strongly Agree</td> <td>81</td> <td>20.4</td> <td>20.4</td> <td>100.0</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Total</td> <td>398</td> <td>100.0</td> <td>100.0</td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>							Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent	Valid	Strongly Disagree	13	3.3	3.3	3.3		Disagree	48	12.1	12.1	15.3		Neutral	116	29.1	29.1	44.5		Agree	140	35.2	35.2	79.6		Strongly Agree	81	20.4	20.4	100.0		Total	398	100.0	100.0	
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent																																											
Valid	Strongly Disagree	13	3.3	3.3	3.3																																											
	Disagree	48	12.1	12.1	15.3																																											
	Neutral	116	29.1	29.1	44.5																																											
	Agree	140	35.2	35.2	79.6																																											
	Strongly Agree	81	20.4	20.4	100.0																																											
	Total	398	100.0	100.0																																												

Table 14.5: Frequency Responses of all the Variables (SPSS version26)

16	Willingness to help patients	<p style="text-align: center;">Responsiveness_Q16</p> <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <thead> <tr> <th colspan="2"></th> <th>Frequency</th> <th>Percent</th> <th>Valid Percent</th> <th>Cumulative Percent</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Valid</td> <td>Strongly Disagree</td> <td>11</td> <td>2.8</td> <td>2.8</td> <td>2.8</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Disagree</td> <td>36</td> <td>9.0</td> <td>9.0</td> <td>11.8</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Neutral</td> <td>119</td> <td>29.9</td> <td>29.9</td> <td>41.7</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Agree</td> <td>140</td> <td>35.2</td> <td>35.2</td> <td>76.9</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Strongly Agree</td> <td>92</td> <td>23.1</td> <td>23.1</td> <td>100.0</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Total</td> <td>398</td> <td>100.0</td> <td>100.0</td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>							Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent	Valid	Strongly Disagree	11	2.8	2.8	2.8		Disagree	36	9.0	9.0	11.8		Neutral	119	29.9	29.9	41.7		Agree	140	35.2	35.2	76.9		Strongly Agree	92	23.1	23.1	100.0		Total	398	100.0	100.0	
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent																																											
Valid	Strongly Disagree	11	2.8	2.8	2.8																																											
	Disagree	36	9.0	9.0	11.8																																											
	Neutral	119	29.9	29.9	41.7																																											
	Agree	140	35.2	35.2	76.9																																											
	Strongly Agree	92	23.1	23.1	100.0																																											
	Total	398	100.0	100.0																																												
17	Readiness to respond to patients 'queries (Flexibility)	<p style="text-align: center;">Responsiveness_Q17</p> <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <thead> <tr> <th colspan="2"></th> <th>Frequency</th> <th>Percent</th> <th>Valid Percent</th> <th>Cumulative Percent</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Valid</td> <td>Strongly Disagree</td> <td>9</td> <td>2.3</td> <td>2.3</td> <td>2.3</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Disagree</td> <td>37</td> <td>9.3</td> <td>9.3</td> <td>11.6</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Neutral</td> <td>105</td> <td>26.4</td> <td>26.4</td> <td>37.9</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Agree</td> <td>163</td> <td>41.0</td> <td>41.0</td> <td>78.9</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Strongly Agree</td> <td>84</td> <td>21.1</td> <td>21.1</td> <td>100.0</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Total</td> <td>398</td> <td>100.0</td> <td>100.0</td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>							Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent	Valid	Strongly Disagree	9	2.3	2.3	2.3		Disagree	37	9.3	9.3	11.6		Neutral	105	26.4	26.4	37.9		Agree	163	41.0	41.0	78.9		Strongly Agree	84	21.1	21.1	100.0		Total	398	100.0	100.0	
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent																																											
Valid	Strongly Disagree	9	2.3	2.3	2.3																																											
	Disagree	37	9.3	9.3	11.6																																											
	Neutral	105	26.4	26.4	37.9																																											
	Agree	163	41.0	41.0	78.9																																											
	Strongly Agree	84	21.1	21.1	100.0																																											
	Total	398	100.0	100.0																																												
Empathy																																																
18	Giving patients individual attention	<p style="text-align: center;">Empathy_Q18</p> <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <thead> <tr> <th colspan="2"></th> <th>Frequency</th> <th>Percent</th> <th>Valid Percent</th> <th>Cumulative Percent</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Valid</td> <td>Strongly Disagree</td> <td>7</td> <td>1.8</td> <td>1.8</td> <td>1.8</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Disagree</td> <td>23</td> <td>5.8</td> <td>5.8</td> <td>7.5</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Neutral</td> <td>132</td> <td>33.2</td> <td>33.2</td> <td>40.7</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Agree</td> <td>160</td> <td>40.2</td> <td>40.2</td> <td>80.9</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Strongly Agree</td> <td>76</td> <td>19.1</td> <td>19.1</td> <td>100.0</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Total</td> <td>398</td> <td>100.0</td> <td>100.0</td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>							Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent	Valid	Strongly Disagree	7	1.8	1.8	1.8		Disagree	23	5.8	5.8	7.5		Neutral	132	33.2	33.2	40.7		Agree	160	40.2	40.2	80.9		Strongly Agree	76	19.1	19.1	100.0		Total	398	100.0	100.0	
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent																																											
Valid	Strongly Disagree	7	1.8	1.8	1.8																																											
	Disagree	23	5.8	5.8	7.5																																											
	Neutral	132	33.2	33.2	40.7																																											
	Agree	160	40.2	40.2	80.9																																											
	Strongly Agree	76	19.1	19.1	100.0																																											
	Total	398	100.0	100.0																																												

Table 14.6: Frequency Responses of all the Variable (SPSS version26)

19	Employees who deal with patients in caring fashion	<p style="text-align: center;">Empathy_Q19</p> <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <thead> <tr> <th colspan="2"></th> <th>Frequency</th> <th>Percent</th> <th>Valid Percent</th> <th>Cumulative Percent</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Valid</td> <td>Strongly Disagree</td> <td>5</td> <td>1.3</td> <td>1.3</td> <td>1.3</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Disagree</td> <td>33</td> <td>8.3</td> <td>8.3</td> <td>9.5</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Neutral</td> <td>121</td> <td>30.4</td> <td>30.4</td> <td>39.9</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Agree</td> <td>159</td> <td>39.9</td> <td>39.9</td> <td>79.9</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Strongly Agree</td> <td>80</td> <td>20.1</td> <td>20.1</td> <td>100.0</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Total</td> <td>398</td> <td>100.0</td> <td>100.0</td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>			Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent	Valid	Strongly Disagree	5	1.3	1.3	1.3		Disagree	33	8.3	8.3	9.5		Neutral	121	30.4	30.4	39.9		Agree	159	39.9	39.9	79.9		Strongly Agree	80	20.1	20.1	100.0		Total	398	100.0	100.0	
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent																																							
Valid	Strongly Disagree	5	1.3	1.3	1.3																																							
	Disagree	33	8.3	8.3	9.5																																							
	Neutral	121	30.4	30.4	39.9																																							
	Agree	159	39.9	39.9	79.9																																							
	Strongly Agree	80	20.1	20.1	100.0																																							
	Total	398	100.0	100.0																																								
20	Having the patient's best interest at heart	<p style="text-align: center;">Empathy_Q20</p> <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <thead> <tr> <th colspan="2"></th> <th>Frequency</th> <th>Percent</th> <th>Valid Percent</th> <th>Cumulative Percent</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Valid</td> <td>Strongly Disagree</td> <td>7</td> <td>1.8</td> <td>1.8</td> <td>1.8</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Disagree</td> <td>33</td> <td>8.3</td> <td>8.3</td> <td>10.1</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Neutral</td> <td>137</td> <td>34.4</td> <td>34.4</td> <td>44.5</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Agree</td> <td>154</td> <td>38.7</td> <td>38.7</td> <td>83.2</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Strongly Agree</td> <td>67</td> <td>16.8</td> <td>16.8</td> <td>100.0</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Total</td> <td>398</td> <td>100.0</td> <td>100.0</td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>			Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent	Valid	Strongly Disagree	7	1.8	1.8	1.8		Disagree	33	8.3	8.3	10.1		Neutral	137	34.4	34.4	44.5		Agree	154	38.7	38.7	83.2		Strongly Agree	67	16.8	16.8	100.0		Total	398	100.0	100.0	
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent																																							
Valid	Strongly Disagree	7	1.8	1.8	1.8																																							
	Disagree	33	8.3	8.3	10.1																																							
	Neutral	137	34.4	34.4	44.5																																							
	Agree	154	38.7	38.7	83.2																																							
	Strongly Agree	67	16.8	16.8	100.0																																							
	Total	398	100.0	100.0																																								
21	Employees who understand the needs of their patients (Right service)	<p style="text-align: center;">Empathy_Q21</p> <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <thead> <tr> <th colspan="2"></th> <th>Frequency</th> <th>Percent</th> <th>Valid Percent</th> <th>Cumulative Percent</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Valid</td> <td>Strongly Disagree</td> <td>8</td> <td>2.0</td> <td>2.0</td> <td>2.0</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Disagree</td> <td>43</td> <td>10.8</td> <td>10.8</td> <td>12.8</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Neutral</td> <td>116</td> <td>29.1</td> <td>29.1</td> <td>42.0</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Agree</td> <td>156</td> <td>39.2</td> <td>39.2</td> <td>81.2</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Strongly Agree</td> <td>75</td> <td>18.8</td> <td>18.8</td> <td>100.0</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Total</td> <td>398</td> <td>100.0</td> <td>100.0</td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>			Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent	Valid	Strongly Disagree	8	2.0	2.0	2.0		Disagree	43	10.8	10.8	12.8		Neutral	116	29.1	29.1	42.0		Agree	156	39.2	39.2	81.2		Strongly Agree	75	18.8	18.8	100.0		Total	398	100.0	100.0	
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent																																							
Valid	Strongly Disagree	8	2.0	2.0	2.0																																							
	Disagree	43	10.8	10.8	12.8																																							
	Neutral	116	29.1	29.1	42.0																																							
	Agree	156	39.2	39.2	81.2																																							
	Strongly Agree	75	18.8	18.8	100.0																																							
	Total	398	100.0	100.0																																								

Table 14.7: Frequency Responses of all the Variables (SPSS version26)

22	Convenient Service Hours	<p style="text-align: center;">Empathy_Q22</p> <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <thead> <tr> <th colspan="2"></th> <th>Frequency</th> <th>Percent</th> <th>Valid Percent</th> <th>Cumulative Percent</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Valid</td> <td>Strongly Disagree</td> <td>7</td> <td>1.8</td> <td>1.8</td> <td>1.8</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Disagree</td> <td>28</td> <td>7.0</td> <td>7.0</td> <td>8.8</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Neutral</td> <td>133</td> <td>33.4</td> <td>33.4</td> <td>42.2</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Agree</td> <td>158</td> <td>39.7</td> <td>39.7</td> <td>81.9</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Strongly Agree</td> <td>72</td> <td>18.1</td> <td>18.1</td> <td>100.0</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Total</td> <td>398</td> <td>100.0</td> <td>100.0</td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>							Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent	Valid	Strongly Disagree	7	1.8	1.8	1.8		Disagree	28	7.0	7.0	8.8		Neutral	133	33.4	33.4	42.2		Agree	158	39.7	39.7	81.9		Strongly Agree	72	18.1	18.1	100.0		Total	398	100.0	100.0	
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent																																											
Valid	Strongly Disagree	7	1.8	1.8	1.8																																											
	Disagree	28	7.0	7.0	8.8																																											
	Neutral	133	33.4	33.4	42.2																																											
	Agree	158	39.7	39.7	81.9																																											
	Strongly Agree	72	18.1	18.1	100.0																																											
	Total	398	100.0	100.0																																												
Service Quality																																																
23	Satisfaction	<p style="text-align: center;">Service_Quality_Q23</p> <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <thead> <tr> <th colspan="2"></th> <th>Frequency</th> <th>Percent</th> <th>Valid Percent</th> <th>Cumulative Percent</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Valid</td> <td>Strongly Disagree</td> <td>8</td> <td>2.0</td> <td>2.0</td> <td>2.0</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Disagree</td> <td>26</td> <td>6.5</td> <td>6.5</td> <td>8.5</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Neutral</td> <td>118</td> <td>29.6</td> <td>29.6</td> <td>38.2</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Agree</td> <td>171</td> <td>43.0</td> <td>43.0</td> <td>81.2</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Strongly Agree</td> <td>75</td> <td>18.8</td> <td>18.8</td> <td>100.0</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Total</td> <td>398</td> <td>100.0</td> <td>100.0</td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>							Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent	Valid	Strongly Disagree	8	2.0	2.0	2.0		Disagree	26	6.5	6.5	8.5		Neutral	118	29.6	29.6	38.2		Agree	171	43.0	43.0	81.2		Strongly Agree	75	18.8	18.8	100.0		Total	398	100.0	100.0	
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent																																											
Valid	Strongly Disagree	8	2.0	2.0	2.0																																											
	Disagree	26	6.5	6.5	8.5																																											
	Neutral	118	29.6	29.6	38.2																																											
	Agree	171	43.0	43.0	81.2																																											
	Strongly Agree	75	18.8	18.8	100.0																																											
	Total	398	100.0	100.0																																												
24	Acceptance	<p style="text-align: center;">Service_Quality_Q24</p> <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <thead> <tr> <th colspan="2"></th> <th>Frequency</th> <th>Percent</th> <th>Valid Percent</th> <th>Cumulative Percent</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Valid</td> <td>Strongly Disagree</td> <td>4</td> <td>1.0</td> <td>1.0</td> <td>1.0</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Disagree</td> <td>29</td> <td>7.3</td> <td>7.3</td> <td>8.3</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Neutral</td> <td>124</td> <td>31.2</td> <td>31.2</td> <td>39.4</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Agree</td> <td>172</td> <td>43.2</td> <td>43.2</td> <td>82.7</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Strongly Agree</td> <td>69</td> <td>17.3</td> <td>17.3</td> <td>100.0</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Total</td> <td>398</td> <td>100.0</td> <td>100.0</td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>							Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent	Valid	Strongly Disagree	4	1.0	1.0	1.0		Disagree	29	7.3	7.3	8.3		Neutral	124	31.2	31.2	39.4		Agree	172	43.2	43.2	82.7		Strongly Agree	69	17.3	17.3	100.0		Total	398	100.0	100.0	
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent																																											
Valid	Strongly Disagree	4	1.0	1.0	1.0																																											
	Disagree	29	7.3	7.3	8.3																																											
	Neutral	124	31.2	31.2	39.4																																											
	Agree	172	43.2	43.2	82.7																																											
	Strongly Agree	69	17.3	17.3	100.0																																											
	Total	398	100.0	100.0																																												

Table 14.8: Frequency Responses of all the Variables (SPSS version26)

25	Intention wants to Return	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th colspan="2"></th> <th colspan="3">Service_Quality_Q25</th> <th>Cumulative</th> </tr> <tr> <th colspan="2"></th> <th>Frequency</th> <th>Percent</th> <th>Valid Percent</th> <th>Percent</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td rowspan="6">Valid</td> <td>Strongly Disagree</td> <td>5</td> <td>1.3</td> <td>1.3</td> <td>1.3</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Disagree</td> <td>27</td> <td>6.8</td> <td>6.8</td> <td>8.0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Neutral</td> <td>94</td> <td>23.6</td> <td>23.6</td> <td>31.7</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Agree</td> <td>190</td> <td>47.7</td> <td>47.7</td> <td>79.4</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Strongly Agree</td> <td>82</td> <td>20.6</td> <td>20.6</td> <td>100.0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Total</td> <td>398</td> <td>100.0</td> <td>100.0</td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>			Service_Quality_Q25			Cumulative			Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Percent	Valid	Strongly Disagree	5	1.3	1.3	1.3	Disagree	27	6.8	6.8	8.0	Neutral	94	23.6	23.6	31.7	Agree	190	47.7	47.7	79.4	Strongly Agree	82	20.6	20.6	100.0	Total	398	100.0	100.0	
		Service_Quality_Q25			Cumulative																																								
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Percent																																								
Valid	Strongly Disagree	5	1.3	1.3	1.3																																								
	Disagree	27	6.8	6.8	8.0																																								
	Neutral	94	23.6	23.6	31.7																																								
	Agree	190	47.7	47.7	79.4																																								
	Strongly Agree	82	20.6	20.6	100.0																																								
	Total	398	100.0	100.0																																									
26	Convenience	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th colspan="2"></th> <th colspan="3">Service_Quality_Q26</th> <th>Cumulative</th> </tr> <tr> <th colspan="2"></th> <th>Frequency</th> <th>Percent</th> <th>Valid Percent</th> <th>Percent</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td rowspan="6">Valid</td> <td>Strongly Disagree</td> <td>19</td> <td>4.8</td> <td>4.8</td> <td>4.8</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Disagree</td> <td>67</td> <td>16.8</td> <td>16.8</td> <td>21.6</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Neutral</td> <td>126</td> <td>31.7</td> <td>31.7</td> <td>53.3</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Agree</td> <td>124</td> <td>31.2</td> <td>31.2</td> <td>84.4</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Strongly Agree</td> <td>62</td> <td>15.6</td> <td>15.6</td> <td>100.0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Total</td> <td>398</td> <td>100.0</td> <td>100.0</td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>			Service_Quality_Q26			Cumulative			Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Percent	Valid	Strongly Disagree	19	4.8	4.8	4.8	Disagree	67	16.8	16.8	21.6	Neutral	126	31.7	31.7	53.3	Agree	124	31.2	31.2	84.4	Strongly Agree	62	15.6	15.6	100.0	Total	398	100.0	100.0	
		Service_Quality_Q26			Cumulative																																								
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Percent																																								
Valid	Strongly Disagree	19	4.8	4.8	4.8																																								
	Disagree	67	16.8	16.8	21.6																																								
	Neutral	126	31.7	31.7	53.3																																								
	Agree	124	31.2	31.2	84.4																																								
	Strongly Agree	62	15.6	15.6	100.0																																								
	Total	398	100.0	100.0																																									
27	No Complaints	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th colspan="2"></th> <th colspan="3">Service_Quality_Q27</th> <th>Cumulative</th> </tr> <tr> <th colspan="2"></th> <th>Frequency</th> <th>Percent</th> <th>Valid Percent</th> <th>Percent</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td rowspan="6">Valid</td> <td>Strongly Disagree</td> <td>14</td> <td>3.5</td> <td>3.5</td> <td>3.5</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Disagree</td> <td>45</td> <td>11.3</td> <td>11.3</td> <td>14.8</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Neutral</td> <td>138</td> <td>34.7</td> <td>34.7</td> <td>49.5</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Agree</td> <td>129</td> <td>32.4</td> <td>32.4</td> <td>81.9</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Strongly Agree</td> <td>72</td> <td>18.1</td> <td>18.1</td> <td>100.0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Total</td> <td>398</td> <td>100.0</td> <td>100.0</td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>			Service_Quality_Q27			Cumulative			Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Percent	Valid	Strongly Disagree	14	3.5	3.5	3.5	Disagree	45	11.3	11.3	14.8	Neutral	138	34.7	34.7	49.5	Agree	129	32.4	32.4	81.9	Strongly Agree	72	18.1	18.1	100.0	Total	398	100.0	100.0	
		Service_Quality_Q27			Cumulative																																								
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Percent																																								
Valid	Strongly Disagree	14	3.5	3.5	3.5																																								
	Disagree	45	11.3	11.3	14.8																																								
	Neutral	138	34.7	34.7	49.5																																								
	Agree	129	32.4	32.4	81.9																																								
	Strongly Agree	72	18.1	18.1	100.0																																								
	Total	398	100.0	100.0																																									
28	Recommend to Others (Word of Mouth)	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th colspan="2"></th> <th colspan="3">Service_Quality_Q28</th> <th>Cumulative</th> </tr> <tr> <th colspan="2"></th> <th>Frequency</th> <th>Percent</th> <th>Valid Percent</th> <th>Percent</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td rowspan="6">Valid</td> <td>Strongly Disagree</td> <td>7</td> <td>1.8</td> <td>1.8</td> <td>1.8</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Disagree</td> <td>23</td> <td>5.8</td> <td>5.8</td> <td>7.5</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Neutral</td> <td>89</td> <td>22.4</td> <td>22.4</td> <td>29.9</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Agree</td> <td>187</td> <td>47.0</td> <td>47.0</td> <td>76.9</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Strongly Agree</td> <td>92</td> <td>23.1</td> <td>23.1</td> <td>100.0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Total</td> <td>398</td> <td>100.0</td> <td>100.0</td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>			Service_Quality_Q28			Cumulative			Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Percent	Valid	Strongly Disagree	7	1.8	1.8	1.8	Disagree	23	5.8	5.8	7.5	Neutral	89	22.4	22.4	29.9	Agree	187	47.0	47.0	76.9	Strongly Agree	92	23.1	23.1	100.0	Total	398	100.0	100.0	
		Service_Quality_Q28			Cumulative																																								
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Percent																																								
Valid	Strongly Disagree	7	1.8	1.8	1.8																																								
	Disagree	23	5.8	5.8	7.5																																								
	Neutral	89	22.4	22.4	29.9																																								
	Agree	187	47.0	47.0	76.9																																								
	Strongly Agree	92	23.1	23.1	100.0																																								
	Total	398	100.0	100.0																																									

Table 14.9: Frequency Responses of all the Variables (SPSS version26)

In overall, Tangibility could be summarized as follow; where tangibility has determined by considering the average of four tangibility indicators for each participant. It's clearly visible from above chart that, only less than 25% of the participants disagree and strongly disagree with tangibility factor while more than 50% of them agree and strongly agree with it.

In overall, Assurance could be summarized as follow; where assurance has determined by considering the average of four assurance indicators for each participant. According to this bar chart, only less than 10% of the participants disagree and strongly disagree with assurance factor while more than 50% of them agree and strongly agree with it.

In overall, Reliability could be summarized as follow; where reliability has determined by considering the average of five reliability indicators for each participant. It's clearly noticeable from above bar chart that, only less than 10% of the participants disagree and strongly disagree with reliability factor while more than 50% of them agree and strongly agree with it.

In overall, Responsiveness could be summarized as follow; where responsiveness has determined by considering the average of four responsiveness indicators for each participant. According to above bar chart, only less than 10% of the participants disagree and strongly disagree with responsiveness factor while more than 50% of them agree and strongly agree with it.

Figure 22.1: Frequency Responses of all the Variables in Bar Chart (SPSS version26)

Figure 22.2: Frequency Responses of all the Variables in Bar Chart (SPSS version26)

4.6 Hypothesis Testing

This section shall discuss the Hypothesis testing, both given variables were normally spread & distributed therefore the correlation coefficient of Pearson was used and measured the relationship of linearity between both independent and dependent variables from the data presented.

Between two variables, based on the rule for correlation, when correlation coefficient is +1 or -1 (either strongly positive or strongly negative) resulted in a perfect relationship whereas correlation coefficient is between +1 and -1 which resulted in moderate or weak relationship between the variables (Mukaka, 2012).

Correlation Coefficient	Strength Description
±0.81 - ±1.00	Strongest
±0.61 - ±0.80	Strong
±0.41 - ±0.60	Moderate
±0.21 - ±0.40	Weak
±0.00 - ±0.20	Weak to No Relationship

Table 15: Rule of Correlation (Hair, et al., 2017) (Mukaka, 2012) (Sekaran.U & Bougie.R, 2016)

4.6.1 Testing Hypothesis H1

As discussed in the Chapter two, supporting Literature review of (Kalubowila, et al., 2017), (Sanjeewa & Senevirathne, 2017), (Punnakitikashem, et al., 2012), (Kalaja, et al., 2016), (Zubayer & Hoque, 2019), (Bosompem Boadi, et al., 2019), (Zun, et al., 2018) & (Arsali, et al., 2008), it is claimed that there is a relationship between Tangibility & Service Quality. Accordingly, in this study researcher has developed hypothesis (H1) and tested it as given below.

H₀: There is no association between Tangibility & Service Quality of OPD at DH Palai Killinochchi District, Sri Lanka

H₁: There is an association between Tangibility & Service Quality of OPD at DH Palai Killinochchi District, Sri Lanka

Decision Rule: *If $p \leq 0.05$, reject H_0*

Correlations

		Tangibility	Service Quality
Tangibility	Pearson Correlation	1	.486**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	398	398
Service Quality	Pearson Correlation	.486**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	398	398

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 16: Statistics of Correlation between Tangibility and Service Quality (SPSS version26)

Null Hypothesis is correct at < 5% of probability, so the Null Hypothesis (H₀) of study could be easily rejected and Alternative Hypothesis (H₁) could be accepted at 95% with confidence level. Pearson's correlation value (r) 0.486, indicates as there is a positive moderate relationship between Tangibility & Service Quality. Specifically, a positive commute in Tangibility is correlated with a positive increment or commute in Service Quality.

Figure 23: The Scatter graph: Tangibility & Service Quality
(SPSS version26)

Figure 23 illustrates the Determination Coefficient, R squared, = 0.236 illustrates that 23.6% of differences / variation in Service Quality is interpreted by Tangibility. The data of Tangibility and Service Quality are angled upwards and not significant of differences, this depicts a positive & moderate relationship & it has conformance with the prior scholars' studies.

4.6.2 Testing Hypothesis H2

As discussed in the Chapter two, supporting Literature review of (Ramseook-Munhurrun, et al., 2010) (Kitapci, et al., 2014), (Narteh, 2017), (Li, et al., 2015), (Fatima, et al., 2019) (Kalubowila, et al., 2017) (Kalaja, et al., 2016) (E.T. Jagoda, et al., 2019), (Bucke, et al., 2020) and (McCreddie, et al., 2021) it is claimed that there is a relationship between Assurance & Service Quality. Accordingly, in this study, researcher has developed hypothesis (H2) and tested it as given below.

H₀: There is no association between Assurance & Service Quality of OPD at DH Palai Killinochchi District, Sri Lanka

H₂: There is an association between Assurance & Service Quality of OPD at DH Palai Killinochchi District, Sri Lanka

Decision Rule: *If $p \leq 0.05$, reject H_0*

		Service Quality	Assurance
Service Quality	Pearson Correlation	1	.547**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	398	398
Assurance	Pearson Correlation	.547**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	398	398

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 17: Statistics of Correlation between Assurance and Service Quality
(SPSS version26)

Null Hypothesis is correct at < 5% of probability, so the Null Hypothesis (H₀) of study could be easily rejected and Alternative Hypothesis (H₂) could be accepted at 95% with confidence level. Therefore, Pearson's correlation value (r) is 0.547 & illustrates as there is a positive & moderate relationship between Assurance & Service Quality. Specifically, a significant positive variation in Assurance is associated with a significant positive increment in Service Quality.

Figure 24: The Scatter graph: Assurance & Service Quality
(SPSS version26)

Figure 24 illustrates the determination coefficient, R squared, = 0.299 reveals that 29.9% of incremental variation in Service Quality which is described by Assurance. The data of Assurance and Service Quality are angled upwards and not significant of differences, this shows a positive & moderate relationship, it has conformance with the prior scholars' studies.

4.6.3 Testing Hypothesis H3

As discussed in the Chapter two, supporting Literature review of (Li, et al., 2015), (Kalaja, et al., 2016), (Sohail, 2003), (Wanninayake , et al., 2019), (Hurtado, et al., 2001), (Arachchi & Kaluarachchi, 2019), (Bucke, et al., 2020), (Subiyakto, et al., 2020) (Mosadeghrad, 2012), (E.T. Jagoda, et al., 2019) and (Anbari, et al., 2014) it is claimed that there is a relationship between Reliability & Service Quality. Accordingly, in this study, researcher has developed hypothesis (H3) and tested it as given below.

H₀: There is no association between Reliability & Service Quality of OPD at DH Palai Killinochchi District, Sri Lanka

H₃: There is an association between Reliability & Service Quality of OPD at DH Palai Killinochchi District, Sri Lanka

Decision Rule: *If $p \leq 0.05$, reject H_0*

Correlations

		Service Quality	Reliability
Service Quality	Pearson Correlation	1	.632**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	398	398
Reliability	Pearson Correlation	.632**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	398	398

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 18: Statistics of Correlation between Reliability and Service Quality
(SPSS version26)

Null Hypothesis is correct at < 5% of probability, so the Null Hypothesis (H_0) of study could be easily rejected and Alternative Hypothesis (H_3) could be accepted at 95% with confidence level. Therefore, Pearson’s correlation value (r) is 0.632 & depicts as there is a positive & strong association between Reliability & Service Quality. More specifically, a positive increment commute in Reliability is correlated as a positive increment in Service Quality.

Figure 25: The Scatter Graph: Reliability & Service Quality
(SPSS version26)

Figure 25 illustrates the determination coefficient, R squared, = 0.399 reveals that 39.9% of difference in Service Quality is described by Reliability. The data of Reliability and Service Quality are angled upwards and not significant of differences, which reveals a positive & strong association as well as it has conformance with the prior scholars' studies.

4.6.4 Testing Hypothesis H4

As discussed in the Chapter two, supporting Literature review of (Arsali, et al., 2008), (Bosompem Boadi, et al., 2019), (Bucke, et al., 2020), (Mahmoud, et al., 2019), (Fatima, et al., 2019), (Sathiyaseelan & Gnanapala, 2015), (Kalaja, et al., 2016), (Li, et al., 2015), (Sadiq Sohail, 2003) and (Purcărea, et al., 2013) it is claimed that there is a relationship between Responsiveness & Service Quality. Accordingly, in this study, researcher has developed hypothesis (H4) and tested it as given below.

H₀: There is no association between Responsiveness & Service Quality of OPD at DH Palai Killinochchi District, Sri Lanka

H₄: There is an association between Responsiveness & Service Quality of OPD at DH Palai Killinochchi District, Sri Lanka

Decision Rule: *If $p \leq 0.05$, reject H_0*

Correlations

		Service Quality	Responsiveness
Service quality	Pearson Correlation	1	.623**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	398	398
Responsiveness	Pearson Correlation	.623**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	398	398

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 19: Statistics of Correlation between Responsiveness and Service Quality
(SPSS version26)

Null Hypothesis is correct at < 5% of probability, so the Null Hypothesis (H₀) of study could be easily rejected and Alternative Hypothesis (H₄) could be accepted at 95%

with confidence level. Therefore, Pearson’s correlation value (r) is 0.623 & shows as there is a positive & strong relationship between Responsiveness & Service Quality. Specifically, a positive incremental commute in Responsiveness is correlated as a positive increment commute in Service Quality.

Figure 26: The Scatter graph: Responsiveness & Service Quality (SPSS version26)

Figure 26 illustrates determination coefficient, R squared, = 0.388 reveals that 38.8% of variation in Service Quality is described by Responsiveness. The data of Responsiveness and Service Quality are angled upwards and not significant of differences, shows a Positive & strong association, it has conformance with the prior scholars’ studies.

4.6.5 Testing Hypothesis H5

As discussed in the Chapter two, supporting Literature review of (Naik, et al., 2013) (Li, et al., 2015) and (Velmurugan, et al., 2019), (Arachchi & Kaluarachchi, 2019), (Sanjeewa & Senevirathne, 2017), (Kalubowila, et al., 2017), (Danasra Dew, et al., 2011) and (Fatima, et al., 2019) it is claimed that there is a relationship between Empathy & Service Quality. Accordingly, in this study, researcher has developed hypothesis (H5) and tested it as given below.

H₀: There is no association between Empathy & Service Quality of OPD at DH Palai Killinochchi District, Sri Lanka

H₅: There is an association between Empathy & Service Quality of OPD at DH Palai Killinochchi District, Sri Lanka

Decision Rule: *If $p \leq 0.05$, reject H_0*

		Service Quality	Empathy
Service Quality	Pearson Correlation	1	.686**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	398	398
Empathy	Pearson Correlation	.686**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	398	398

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 20: Statistics of Correlation between Responsiveness & Service Quality (SPSS version26)

Null Hypothesis is correct at < 5% of probability, so the Null Hypothesis (H₀) of study could be easily rejected and Alternative Hypothesis (H₅) could be accepted at 95% with confidence level. Therefore, Pearson’s correlation value (r) is 0.686 & shows as there is a strong positive correlation between Empathy and Service Quality. In other words, a positive increment commute in Empathy is correlated as a positive incremental commute in Service Quality.

Figure 27: The Scatter graph: Empathy & Service Quality (SPSS version26)

Figure 27 illustrates determination coefficient, R squared, = 0.471 reveals as 47.1% differences in Service Quality is described by Empathy. The data of Empathy & Service Quality are angled upwards and not significant of differences, shows a positive & strong relationship, it has conformance with the prior scholars' studies.

4.7 Outline of the Correlation of the Variables

		Correlations					
		Tangibility	Assurance	Reliability	Responsiveness	Empathy	Service Quality
Tangibility	Pearson Correlation	1	.563**	.514**	.512**	.463**	.486**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001
	N	398	398	398	398	398	398
Assurance	Pearson Correlation	.563**	1	.635**	.580**	.626**	.547**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001		<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001
	N	398	398	398	398	398	398
Reliability	Pearson Correlation	.514**	.635**	1	.673**	.627**	.632**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001	<.001		<.001	<.001	<.001
	N	398	398	398	398	398	398
Responsiveness	Pearson Correlation	.512**	.580**	.673**	1	.716**	.623**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001	<.001	<.001		<.001	<.001
	N	398	398	398	398	398	398
Empathy	Pearson Correlation	.463**	.626**	.627**	.716**	1	.686**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001		<.001
	N	398	398	398	398	398	398
Service Quality	Pearson Correlation	.486**	.547**	.632**	.623**	.686**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001	
	N	398	398	398	398	398	398

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 21: Correlation Variables report (SPSS version26)

4.8 Exploration of Multiple-Linear Regression

ANOVA Table 23 shows as the p-value: 0.000 & is < the threshold value (p-value<0.05) indicates as the integrated model (multi linear model) as Statistically Important & significant, hence can be accepted

Variables Entered/Removed

Model	Variables Entered	Variables Removed	Method
1	Empathy, Tangibility, Reliability, Assurance, Responsiveness ^b	.	Enter

a. Dependent Variable: Service Quality

b. All requested variables entered.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.745 ^a	.556	.550	.54615

a. Predictors: (Constant), Empathy, Tangibility, Reliability, Assurance, Responsiveness

b. Dependent Variable: Service Quality

Table 22: The Variables Entered & Model Report for all the variables (SPSS version26)

Based on table 22, shows as Dependent Variable of Service Quality was given a good projection by five variables of Tangibility, Assurance, Reliability, Responsiveness and

Empathy. The adjusted R squared of 0.550 indicates that 55.0% of variance in dependent variable is described by the five independent variables.

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	146.221	5	29.244	98.041	<.001 ^b
	Residual	116.927	392	.298		
	Total	263.148	397			

a. Dependent Variable: Service Quality

b. Predictors: (Constant), Empathy, Tangibility, Reliability, Assurance, Responsiveness

Table 23: ANOVA: All variables (SPSS version26)

According to the above output, p-value = 0.000 which is less than 5% significance level. Hence there is enough evidence to conclude that the fitted multiple linear regression model is statistically significant at 5% level.

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.656	.149		4.410	<.001
	Tangibility	.099	.038	.111	2.608	.009
	Assurance	.024	.051	.023	.471	.638
	Reliability	.242	.051	.240	4.718	<.001
	Responsiveness	.100	.048	.113	2.091	.037
	Empathy	.376	.051	.389	7.400	<.001

a. Dependent Variable: service Quality

Table 24: Coefficients: All variables (SPSS version26)

Based on table 24 reveals the regression coefficients and significance tests for each of the independent variables in the model. Tangibility, Reliability, and Empathy are the

significant variables in this model as they consist of p values; 0.009, 0.000, and 0.000 respectively which are less than 5%. But assurance and responsiveness have the p-values of 0.638 and 0.037 respectively, greater than 5% of significance. This indicates assurance and responsiveness are statistically insignificant predictors to service quality in the combined model even though Pearson’s correlation validated the individual relationship with service quality.

Considering the estimates, the regression coefficients are literally interpreted as “For every additional unit increase in Tangibility, Reliability, and Empathy, the Service quality will be increased by 0.099, 0.242, and 0.376 respectively.

4.9 Proposed New Model excluding Assurance and Responsiveness

Since assurance and responsiveness were found as insignificant predictors for service quality in the above fitted multiple linear regression model, a new model excluding Assurance and responsiveness was proposed.

Variables Entered/Removed^a

Model	Variables Entered	Variables Removed	Method
1	Empathy, Tangibility, Reliability ^b	.	Enter

a. Dependent Variable: Service_Quality

b. All requested variables entered.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.742 ^a	.550	.547	.54800

a. Predictors: (Constant), Empathy, Tangibility, Reliability

Table 25: Coefficients: All variables in New Model (SPSS version26)

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	144.826	3	48.275	160.753	.000 ^b
	Residual	118.322	394	.300		
	Total	263.148	397			

a. Dependent Variable: Service_Quality
b. Predictors: (Constant), Empathy, Tangibility, Reliability

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.685	.144		4.765	.000
	Tangibility	.118	.036	.133	3.308	.001
	Reliability	.285	.046	.283	6.167	.000
	Empathy	.432	.043	.447	10.079	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Service_Quality

Table 26: ANOVA: All variables in New Model (SPSS version26)

As described above outputs of the new proposed model, the adjusted R squared value is 0.5480 which is marginally increased by 0.0019 from the previously fitted model. Therefore, this difference can be considered insignificant. Since the proposed new model has adjusted R squared value with a negligible difference, it's better to remain with the previous model of five independent variables.

As illustrated in table: 24, Value B, identified as one unit of increment in Tangibility, Assurance, Reliability Responsiveness & Empathy will increase 0.099, 0.024, 0.242, 0.100 and 0.376 units in Perceived Service Quality respectively. In deference with the above stated findings, have formulated the sum of multiple-linear regression model based on the research as given beneath.

$\text{Perceived Service Quality} = .656 + .099 (\text{Tangibility}) + .024 (\text{Assurance}) + .242 (\text{Reliability}) + .100 (\text{Responsiveness}) + .376 (\text{Empathy})$
--

4.10 Final Report of Hypothesis

Hypothesis Number	Hypothesis	Alternative	Null	Relationship	Correlation coefficient
H1	Relationship Tangibility to Perceived Service Quality	Accepted	Rejected	Moderate Positive	$r = 0.486$
H2	Relationship Assurance to Perceived Service Quality	Accepted	Rejected	Moderate Positive	$r = 0.547$
H3	Relationship Reliability to Perceived Service Quality	Accepted	Rejected	Strong Positive	$r = 0.632$
H4	Relationship Responsiveness to Perceived Service Quality	Accepted	Rejected	Strong Positive	$r = 0.623$
H5	Relationship Empathy to Perceived Service Quality	Accepted	Rejected	Strong Positive	$r = 0.686$

Table 27: Report of Hypothesis Test Table

5 Chapter Five

5.1 Conclusion & Suggestion

5.1.1 Summary of Study

This testing was conducted as an empirical approach to examine the factors influencing Perceived Healthcare Service Quality of OPD at DH Palai, Killinochchi District, Sri Lanka. The study was conducted based on a significant reduction in usage of OPD services since the later part of 2019, which reflected in decreases in OPD Patients (Figure 2).

There were several complaints made in several media, including social media on healthcare services of DH Palai. Unfortunately, the early part of the 2020 Pandemic Covid 19 spread in Sri Lanka brought further implications on healthcare services such as infection to the Staff, followed by strict imposed Quarantine procedures on them, which made the healthcare services further compromised especially OPD of DH Palai. Simultaneously, frequent healthcare staff strikes also occurred, which also affected the Service Quality of the OPD at DH Palai.

Therefore, the researcher understood the importance of Service Quality in Healthcare & has interested in improving the Service Quality of the OPD; which researcher has assumed that there should be a significant impact on Service Quality due to several factors. This led to doing the Cross-Sectional study to find the answers for the research questions, which eventually formed the Research Objectives of this Study (Chapter one).

Based on the rigorous critical literature reviews on both Sri Lankan and International based similar studies conducted for assessing the healthcare perceived service quality. The researcher has identified Service Quality as a dependent variable, and five independent variables that are most closely associated with Service Quality are Tangibility, Assurance, Reliability, Responsiveness & Empathy based on frequency (which is the first objective of this study).

Accordingly, five hypotheses were formulated based on the conceptual model to examine through the statistical analysis to test the relationship between the independent & Dependent variables. This has led to forming the Questionnaire Survey (Appendix 1) and identified the unique indicators to examine each variable and has mentioned in the operationalization.

The sample size was 374 calculated through Morgan's sample size calculator to represent the targeted population which is 14504 and collected 398, and all of them were used since even for the larger population, it is 384. The simple random sampling methodology has been used & which is simple and easy to generalize the population.

Internal consistency test done for the Reliability & accuracy of the data gathered and detailed descriptive statistics analysis performed for the frequency study of the feedback. Tests of Skewness, Kurtosis were done to examine the pattern of distribution of data. Finally, a multi-collinearity test was conducted to examine the relation between the independent variables.

Data clustered were examined at 95% Confidence level through Pearson's correlation statistical analysis and multiple-linear regression. All of the Null hypotheses were rejected, & Alternative Hypotheses were accepted, this has proposed that all the five independent variables have positive moderate and strong relationships as the dependent variable (reached second objective of study).

Moreover, multiple-linear regression showed that the dependent variable (Perceived Service Quality) was affected by five independent variables. However, in this study, the variables Tangibility, Assurance, Reliability, Responsiveness, and Empathy individually influence the Service quality of OPD; when we consider these variables collectively in the model, we found that only Tangibility, Reliability and Empathy are the significant predictors for Service quality of OPD.

In contrast, Assurance and Responsiveness are statistically insignificant predictors to perceived service quality in the combined model (achieved third objective of research).

5.1.2 Research Conclusion

According to the Statistical data analysis & presentation, revealed in chapter four, Impacts & relationships were recognised between both independent & dependent variables; the investigator has made the following verdict for each set of independent & dependent variables of this study.

5.1.2.1 Tangibility vs Perceived Service Quality

According to the Correlation study, the correlation value (r) = 0.486 showed a positive and moderate association between tangibility & service quality. Based on linear-regression, coefficient of determination, R squared, = 0.236 revealed that Tangibility had explained 23.6% of the variation in Service Quality. Further multiple regression results indicated that a one-unit increase in Tangibility should increase 0.099 units in Service Quality.

Literature reviews in chapter two also support this finding (Kalubowila, et al., 2017), (Sanjeeva & Senevirathne, 2017), (Punnakitikashem, et al., 2012), (Kalaja, et al., 2016). Moreover, it confirmed that Tangibility is an influencing factor on service quality.

The mean value for the complete study sample revealed 3.5879 for the Tangibility showed 50% of the respondents agreed or strongly agreed. Indicators such as Modern Equipment (36.2%), Appealing Facilities (35.9%), Professional Appearance (28.9%) & Appealing Material (23.9%) were rated neutrally; hence It implies rest are around 50 %, including neutral or not agree, which states that there is a room for the improvement in Tangibility concerning Service Quality.

5.1.2.2 Assurance vs Perceived Service Quality

Based on the relationship study, the value (r) of correlation = 0.547 revealed a positive & moderate relationship between assurance & service quality. According to the linear-regression, coefficient of determination, R squared, = 0.299 revealed as 29.9% the variation in Service Quality had been explained by Assurance. Simultaneously multiple regression results revealed that one-unit increase in Assurance should increase 0.024 units in Service Quality.

Literature reviews in chapter two also support this (Ramseook-Munhurrun, et al., 2010) (Kitapci, et al., 2014), (Narteh, 2017), (Li, et al., 2015), (Fatima, et al., 2019) (Kalubowila, et al., 2017) (Kalaja, et al., 2016) (E.T. Jagoda, et al., 2019), (Bucke, et al., 2020) and confirmed that Assurance is a critical factor on service quality.

The mean value for the complete study sample revealed 3.7889 for the Assurance, which showed that 50% of the respondents agreed or strongly agreed and only less than 10 % disagreed. Indicators such as Confident in Patients (31.9%), Comfortability (36.7%),

Dignified Staff (29.6 %) & Knowledge on Queries (29.1%) were rated neutrally; hence It implies that rest are around 50 % including neutral or not agree, which states that there is a room for the improvement in Assurance concerning Service Quality.

5.1.2.3 Reliability vs Perceived Service Quality

Depending on the correlation-study, value (r) of correlation = 0.632 testified a positive & strong association between reliability & service quality. According to the linear-regression, coefficient of determination, R squared, = 0.399 revealed as Reliability explains 39.9% of the variation in Service Quality. Further, multiple regression results revealed that one-unit increase in Reliability should increase 0.242 units in Service Quality.

Literature reviews in chapter two also support this finding (Li, et al., 2015), (Kalaja, et al., 2016), (Sohail, 2003), (Wanninayake , et al., 2019), (Hurtado, et al., 2001), (Arachchi & Kaluarachchi, 2019), (Bucke, et al., 2020), (Subiyakto, et al., 2020) (Mosadeghrad, 2012), (E.T. Jagoda, et al., 2019) and confirmed that Reliability is a crucial factor on service quality.

The mean value for the complete sample of the study revealed 3.6608 for the Reliability, which showed that 50% of the respondents agreed or strongly agreed and only less than 10 % disagreed. Indicators such as Promised Service (30.9%), Ensured Service (30.9%), Informed Right Service (33.6 %), Right Service on Time (29.1%) & Accurate Records (29.6%) were rated neutrally; hence It implies rest are around 50 % including neutral or not agree, which states that there is a room for the improvement in Reliability concerning Service Quality.

5.1.2.4 Responsiveness vs Perceived Service Quality

After the correlation study, value (r) of correlation 0.623 revealed a positive & strong relationship between responsiveness & service quality. Based on the linear-regression, coefficient of determination, R squared, = 0.388 revealed as 38.8% variation in Service Quality had been explained by responsiveness. Further, multiple regression results revealed as one-unit increase in responsiveness should increase 0.100 units in Service Quality.

Literature reviews in chapter two also support this finding (Bosompem Boadi, et al., 2019), (Bucke, et al., 2020), (Mahmoud, et al., 2019), (Fatima, et al., 2019), (Sathiyaseelan & Gnanapala, 2015), (Kalaja, et al., 2016), (Li, et al., 2015), (Sadiq Sohail, 2003) and (Purcărea, et al., 2013) confirmed that responsiveness is an essential factor on service quality.

The mean value for the complete sample of the study revealed 3.6985 for the responsiveness, showing that 50% of the respondents agreed or strongly agreed and only less than 10 % disagreed. Indicators such as Informed Service (32.7%), Prompt Service (29.1%), Willingness on Help (29.9%) & Preparedness (26.4%) were rated neutrally; hence It implies that rest are around 50 %, including neutral or not agree, which states that there is a room for the improvement in responsiveness for Service Quality.

5.1.2.5 Empathy vs Perceived Service Quality

It has been observed in the correlation study as value (r) of correlation = 0.686 revealed as there is a positive and strong association between empathy & service quality. According to the linear-regression, coefficient of determination, R squared, = 0.471 revealed as 47.1% of the variation in Service Quality had been explained by empathy. Further, multiple regression results revealed as one-unit increase in empathy should increase 0.376 units in Service Quality.

Literature reviews in chapter two also support this finding (Naik, et al., 2013) (Li, et al., 2015) and (Velmurugan, et al., 2019), (Arachchi & Kaluarachchi, 2019), (Sanjeewa & Senevirathne, 2017), (Kalubowila, et al., 2017), (Danasra Dew, et al., 2011) and (Fatima, et al., 2019) confirmed that empathy is an essential factor on service quality.

The mean value for the complete study sample revealed 3.6407 for the empathy that showed 50% of the respondents agreed or strongly agreed and only less than 10 % disagreed. Indicators such as Specific Attention (33.2%), Caring Fashion (30.4%), Patient Best Interest (34.4%), Understand Needs (29.1%) & Service Hours (33.4%) were rated neutrally; hence It implies rest are around 50 %, including neutral or not agree, which states that there is a room for the improvement in empathy to Service Quality.

5.1.2.6 Summary of Conclusion

Even though, as mentioned above, the variables Tangibility, Assurance, Reliability, Responsiveness, and Empathy individually influence Service quality of OPD, when we consider these variables collectively in the model, we found that only Tangibility, Reliability and Empathy are the significant predictors for Service quality of OPD.

When these factors were graphically represented, the presently fulfilled degrees at OPD at DH Palai were identified based on “Agree” and “Strongly agree” responses for the corresponding factors. So that Tangibility, Assurance, Reliability, Responsiveness, and Empathy factors are fulfilled 55.5%, 66.3%, 60.8%, 61.6% and 58.3% respectively at OPD at DH Palai. It has also been observed that level of confidence to use the OPD services through the Service Quality assessed preferably with Intention to Return (68.3% agree or strongly agree) & Recommend to Others (Word of Mouth) (69.4% agree or strongly agree) (Fourth Objectives Achieved).

5.2 Recommendation

Based on the conclusion arrived from this study & the descriptive statistics the following could be forwarded to improve the Tangibility, Assurance, Reliability, Responsiveness, and Empathy to optimize the Perceived Service Quality of OPD service of DH Palai (Final Objective of this study).

5.2.1 Recommendation to Improve the Tangibility

As discussed in conclusion above, the Administration of DH Palai & RDHS of Killinochchi should focus on each indicator of Tangibility to improve the Service Quality. Adequate fund allocation to improve the basic needs of Infrastructure development & staff development such as providing additional instruments, mobile ultrasound scan, mobile X-ray machine, adequate space, standardized directions & informative banners. Organized reception with adequate facilities like OPD digital registration, adequate seating facilities including for differently-abled patients (wheelchairs, lift), Providing health information and updates via Telemedicine technology (Punia, et al., 2020). Facilitate on 5 S & KAIZEN principles in the OPD premises & Operation Management. Provide Adequate training to health staff on infrastructure development & professionalism.

5.2.2 Recommendation to Improve the Assurance

As stated in conclusion, the Healthcare system, in general, should undergo an acceptable benchmark practiced throughout the international platform; the researcher proposes to establish the Standardized practice in OPD services with specific international accreditation such as JCI. It is also recommended to the Health Staff of the DH Palai to keep up the Continued Professional Development (CPD) on patient safety, ethics, skills, sustainability of such practice with enthusiasm & team spirit. Install the back referral system & Concern Box to Administration for the uniformed sustainable services. Provide adequate training & audit with the system systematically to avoid collapse. Keeping up the good working culture in the hospital with a reward system & adequate payment to the health staff eventually increases the assurance, therefore, Service quality.

5.2.3 Recommendation to Improve the Reliability

As described in conclusion, this study's reliability indicator should be taken into account by hospital & regional administration together to optimize the reliability of the service. Management should at least provide adequate staff to ensure sustainable services. Human resources are the major problem in DH Palai, where lack of staff provides sustainable services without failure of the healthcare system of DH Palai. Therefore, RDHS, PDHS, Ministry of Health and Public Service Commission should pay concern to the primary healthcare system strengthening program to operate the system to provide required prompt services such as staff allocation, digital technology for recording patient's details, internet facilities, and printing system communication facilities.

5.2.4 Recommendation to Improve the Responsiveness

As stated in conclusion, responsiveness is another essential factor influencing Service Quality; hence, indicators of responsiveness are beneficial to improve the quality of service provided. While concerning all indicators, it is better to provide an organized healthcare delivery system via KAIZEN, Queuing & Lean principles to improve the regularized OPD services at DH Palai. Administration of Institution & RDHS should audit the system infrequently in order to sustain the Informed, Prompt Service. It has also

considered establishing the workshop, in-service training, appraisal & rewarding techniques to improve the Willingness on Help & Preparedness of the Staff & management.

5.2.5 Recommendation to Improve the Empathy

One of the essential components of Healthcare Service Quality to be considered is always keeping up the higher standard of such practice in the hospital. It is better to organize the staff and management together and revisit the goal and improve the empathy indicators collectively. It also needs to periodically provide the staff with rigorous training & strict ethics principles on patient safety and healthcare quality. To guide them & organize the more socially engaged activities to show the helping tendency of the hospital, such as free medical camps, medical education to the rural area & provide adequate services to an aging population. The administration also should consider providing OPD services at night and emergency services, eventually improving the quality of services.

Recommendation to Medical Administrators of the Northern Province

(MOIC, DMO, MOH, RDHS, PDHS, Health Secretary and Stakeholders)

Based on literature reviews, descriptive statistics, & study findings above mentioned audience should focus on following,

Majority of the OPD patients are female, middle aged, married with at least two children; Earning capacity is very much low (< 25000 Rs) and most of them are from the rural area (85%).

Therefore, which leads them to use the DH Palai as a primary healthcare institution (72%) for their medical problems. Create an organized & sustainable patients welfare society, where the public take the role of cooperative support on fundraising, protect the rights of patients, harmonize the agitation from the public or media, voluntary services on Hospital environment maintenance with the support of hospital administration.

Apply the needed Strategies to solve the current problems especially on staff shortage, so Prioritizing the annual transfer replacement for the working forces to sustain the healthcare services, it is possible via having a continuous allocation of staff with the help

of Government Medical Officer Association (GMOA), Nursing Council, Paramedical Council, & Public service commission.

Propose to use the intern qualified doctors, nurses, reemployment for retired health staff or apprentice on voluntary or contract basis to overcome the staff shortage.

Provide health education to OPD patients, which can bring positive result in OPD services. effective & efficient use of social media under the regulatory support from the health ministry on marketing the DH Palai for the good causes eventually will results in satisfactory reputation.

Adequate Safety measures with Effective & efficient Healthcare services

Service-oriented trained & adequate human resources with Learning updates

Systematic approaches towards the Patients centred Healthcare delivery

Evidence-Based Practices & comprehensive Services with technology

The Medical Education curriculum exhibits multi-disciplinary approaches

Efficient Waste management system with local urban council

Benchmarking of Standardised Health Care services.

Establish vigilant referring & monitoring bodies.

5.3 Suggestions & Future Research

This study has been conducted within a limited time frame for the educational purpose as a Cross-Sectional Study but better to consider a Longitudinal study in future for a better understanding of Service Quality.

It is only quantitative deductive applied research with a simple random sampling technique, which has considered the patients' aspects through the questionnaire only and not through the Interviews or focused group discussion as a qualitative study, which could provide better understanding of the healthcare services.

This study did not include the Staff, Administrators or stakeholders to observe the more comprehensive responses. It has been recommended to include all the staff & management of the DH Palai, Stakeholders to have a better result.

The study has assessed only the OPD services of DH Palai, which has not considered the Emergency care, Ward Management, Pharmacy, Maternity & other Clinic Services. It is better to include all services to assess the actual DH Palai service quality.

This research was conducted only in the OPD service of DH Palai but recommended considering all the Divisional Hospitals (DH) (C- Grade) on Kilinochchi & Island wide to observe the reliable result.

A study was conducted as an individual study, if the Ministry of Health is involved in such systematic study, more detailed findings could be achieved.

Due to Covid -19 pandemic, patients were not cooperative and most of the patients are known to the researcher, therefore, is recommended to use another third party from PDHS or RDHS office to avoid the bias of the study.

6 References

1. A.H. Nor Aziati & Binti Hamdan, N. S., 2018. *Application Of Queuing Theory Model And Simulation To Patient Flow At The Outpatient Department*. s.l., EOM Society International.
2. Aagia, J. & Garg, R., 2010. Measuring perceived service quality for public hospitals (PubHosQual) in the Indian context. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical and Healthcare Marketing*, 4(1), pp. 60-83.
3. Anbari, Z., Mohammadi, M. & Taheri, M., 2014. Measurement of Quality of Hospital Services via SERVQUAL Model. *Life Science Journal*, 11(6).
4. Arachchi, D. E. & Kaluarachchi, I. P., 2019. Ayurveda Medical Tourism in Sri Lanka: Service Quality and Service Satisfaction. *Journal of Tourism Economics and Applied Research*, 3(1), pp. 1-7.
5. Arsali, H., Ekiz, E. & Katircioglu, S., 2008. Gearing service quality into public and private hospitals in small islands. *International Journal of Health Care Quality Assurance*, 21(1), pp. 8-23.
6. Borkowski, N. & Meese, K. A., 2021. *Organizational Behaviour in Healthcare*. 4 ed. s.l.:s.n.
7. Bosompem Boadi, E., Wenxin, W., Bentum-Micah, G. & Jerry Asare, I. K., 2019. Impact of Service Quality on Customer Satisfaction in Ghana hospitals: A PLS-SEM Approach. *Canadian Journal of Applied Science & Technology*, 7(3), pp. 503-511.
8. Bounthavong, M., 2019. *Mark Bounthavong*. [Online] Available at: <https://mbounthavong.com> [Accessed January 2022].
9. Bucke, V., Ruzevicius, J. & Buckus, R., 2020. Service Quality Management at Lithuanian Healthcare Institutions. *Proquest*, 21(174).
10. Chatterji, P. & Li, Y., 2020. Effects of the Covid-19 Pandemic on Outpatients Providers in US. *NBER working paper series*.
11. Chi, Y. & Quan, Y., 2013. *Service Quality Perspective and Customer Satisfaction: Xingya Technical Communication Company*, s.l.: University of Galve.
12. Corrigan, J., 2001. Crossing the Quality Chasm. In: *Building a Better Delivery System: A New Engineering/Health Care Partnership*. s.l.:s.n., pp. 95-97.
13. Danasra Dew, F., Sudjana, G. & Marty Oesman, Y., 2011. Patient satisfaction analysis on service quality of dental health care based on empathy and responsiveness. *Dental Research Journal*, 8(4), pp. 172-177.
14. Department of Census & Statistics, 2012. *Poppulaion by ethnicity and district according to Divisional Secretary`s Division*, s.l.: Sri Lanka Census of Population & Housing 2011.

15. DHQS, 2020. *Brief History of Organization, Directorate of Health care Quality and Safety*. [Online]
Available at: <https://quality.health.gov.lk>
[Accessed 2021].
16. District Secretariat-Killinochchi, 2021. *Statistical Hand Book 2021*, s.l.: s.n.
17. E.T. Jagoda, E.A.K.K. Edirisinghe & M.K.D.L. Meegoda, 2019. *Evaluation of Service Quality in Nursing and Patient Satisfaction: Perception of Patients & Student Nurses*. s.l., TIIKM, pp. 37-51.
18. Family Health Bureau, 2020. *National Statistics*, s.l.: Family Health Bureau, Sri Lanka.
19. Fatima, I., Humayun, A., Iqbal, U. & Shafiq, M., 2019. Dimensions of service quality in healthcare: a systematic review of literature. *International Journal for Quality in Health Care*, 31(1), pp. 11-29.
20. Fernando, D., 2000. Health care systems in transition III. Sri Lanka, Part I. An overview of Sri Lanka's health care system. *Journal of Public Health Medicine*, 22(1), p. 14–20.
21. Geberu, D. M., Biks., A. G., Gebremedhin, T. & Mekonnen, T. H., 2019. Factors of patient satisfaction in adult outpatient departments of private wing and regular services in public hospitals of Addis Ababa, Ethiopia: a comparative cross-sectional study. *BMC Health Services Research*, 19(869), pp. 1-13.
22. Gusmano, M. K., Maschke, K. J. & Solomon, M. . Z., 2019. Patient-Centered Care, Yes; Patients As Consumers, No. *Health Affairs*, 38(3), pp. 368-373.
23. Hair, J, et al., 2016. *The Essentials of Business Research Method*. 3 ed. New York: Routledge.
24. Hair, . J., Hult, G., Ringle, C. & Sarstedt, M., 2017. *A Primer on Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM)*. 2 ed. CA: Thousand Oaks.
25. Howell, C., 2012. *Printwand*. [Online]
Available at: <https://www.printwand.com/blog/how-customer-service-creates-value>
[Accessed 1 January 2022].
26. Hurtado, M. P., Swift, E. K. & Corrigan., J. M., 2001. *Envisioning the National Health Care Quality Report*, s.l.: IOM.
27. Kalaja, R., Myshketa, R. & Scalera, F., 2016. Service quality assessment in health care sector: the case of Durres public hospital. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, Volume 235, pp. 557-565.
28. Kalubowila, K. C. et al., 2017. Patient satisfaction of services at the out-patient department of Base Hospital Panadura, Sri Lanka. *Journal of the College of Community Physicians of Sri Lanka*, 23(2).
29. Kitapci, O., Akdogan, C. & Dortyol, İ. T., 2014. The Impact of Service Quality Dimensions on Patient Satisfaction, Repurchase intentions and Word-of-Mouth Communication in the Public Healthcare Industry. *ScienceDirec*, Volume 148, pp. 161-169.

30. Kohn, L. T., Corrigan, J. M. & Donaldson, M. S., 2000. Building a Safer Health System. In: *to err is human*. s.l.:IOM.
31. KumarRoy, S., Shekhar, V., M.Lassar, W. & Chen, T., 2018. Customer engagement behaviors: The role of service convenience, fairness and quality. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, Volume 44, pp. 293-304.
32. Likert, 1932. A Technique for the Measurement of Attitude. *Archive of Psychology*, Volume 140, pp. 1-50.
33. Li, M. et al., 2015. Evaluating Patients`perception of service quality at hospitals in nine chinese cities by use of SERVQUAL scale. *Asian Pacific Journal of Tropical Biomedicine*, 5(6), pp. 497-504.
34. Li, Y. & Shang, H., 2019. Service quality, perceived value, and citizens` continuous-use intention regarding e-government: Empirical evidence from China. *Information & Management*.
35. Mahmoud, A. B., Ekwere, T., Fuxman, L. & Ahmad Meero, A., 2019. Assessing Patients` Perception of Health Care Service Quality Offered by COHSASA-Accredited Hospitals in Nigeria. *SAGE Open*.
36. McCreddie, M., Benwel, B. & Gritti, A., 2021. A qualitative study of National Health Service (NHS) complaint-responses. *BMC Health Services Research*, 21(696).
37. Ministry of Health, 1994. *Manual on Management of District Hospitals, Peripheral Units & Rural Hospitals*, s.l.: Ministry of Health.
38. Ministry of Health, 2018. *Reorganising Primary Health Care in Sri Lanka*, s.l.: s.n.
39. Ministry of Home Affairs & Divisional Secretariat Pachchilaipalli, 2021. *Total Population of Pachchilaipalli*, s.l.: s.n.
40. Mirror, C., 2020. *Ceylon Mirror*. [Online]
Available at: <https://ceylonmirror.lk/>
[Accessed 15 January 2022].
41. Mosadeghrad, A. M., 2012. A Conceptual Framework for Quality of Care. *Mat Soc Med*, 24(4), pp. 251-261.
42. Mukaka, M., 2012. Statistics Corner: A guide to appropriate use of Correlation coefficient in medical research. *Malawi Medical Journal*, 24(3), pp. 69-71.
43. N.Ross, K., 2005. Sample Design for Educational Survey Research. In: s.l.:s.n.
44. Naik, J. R. K., Anan, D. B. & Bashi, I., 2013. Healthcare Service Quality and word of mouth: Key drivers to achieve Patient Satisfaction. *Pacific Business Review International*, 5(2).
45. Nakarvu, 2022. *Nakarvu*. [Online]
Available at: nkarvu.com/158128/
[Accessed 10 01 2022].

46. Narteh, B., 2017. Service quality and customer satisfaction in Ghanaian retail banks: the moderating role of price. *International Journal of Bank Marketing*, 36(1), pp. 68-88.
47. Oliver. R. L., 1980. Cognitive Model of the Antecedents of Satisfaction Decisions. *Journal of Marketing Research*, Volume 17, pp. 46-49.
48. Orcan, F., 2020. arametric or Non-parametric: Skewness to Test Normality for Mean Comparison. *International Journal of Assessment Tools in Education*, 7(2), pp. 255-265.
49. Parasuraman, A., Zeithamal, V. A. & L.Berry, L., 1985. A Conceptual Model of Service Quality and Its Implications for Future Research. *Journal of Marketing*, Volume 49, pp. 41-50.
50. Parasuraman, A., Z. V. & B. L., 1988. SERVQUAL: a multiple-item scale for measuring consumer perceptions of service quality. *Journal of Retailing*, 64(1), pp. 5-40.
51. Perera, A. & Perera, H., 2017. *Primary Healthcare Systems*, s.l.: WHO.
52. Punia, V., Zagorski, V. & Fesler, J., 2020. Evidence of a Rapid Shift in Outpatient Practice During the COVID-19 Pandemic Using Telemedicine. *TELEMEDICINE and e-HEALT*, 26(10).
53. Punnakitikashem, P., Buavaraporn, N., Maluesri, P. & Leelartapin, K., 2012. *Health Care Service Quality: Case Example of a Hospital with Lean Implementation*. s.l., s.n.
54. Purcărea, V. L., Gheorgh, I. R. & Petrescu, C. M., 2013. *The Assessment of Perceived Service Quality of Public Health Care Services in Romania Using the SERVQUAL Scale*. s.l., Elsevier, pp. 573-585.
55. Q. D., 2022. s.l.:s.n.
56. Ramseook-Munhurrun, P., Naidoo, P. & Lukea-Bhiwajee, S. D., 2010. Measuring Service Quality: Perceptions of Employees. *Global Journal of Business Research*, 4(1).
57. Rengarajan, V., Sangararaman, G., Surulivel, S. & Dinesh, S., 2019. Service Quality Of Airtel Mobile Operator Using Servqual Model In Kanchipuram District, Tamil Nadu. *International Journal of Scientific Technology Research*, 8(10).
58. Rezaei, S. et al., 2018. Service quality in Iranian hospitals: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Medical Journal of the Islamic Republic of Iran*, 32(59).
59. Sadiq Sohail, M., 2003. Service quality in hospitals: more favourable than you think. *Managing Service Quality*, 13(3), pp. 197-206.
60. Sanjeeva, C. & Senevirathne, R., 2017. Assessment of Patient Satisfaction Using OPD Service at the Out Patients Department - Case Study - at Teaching Hospital Karapitiya Sri Lanka. *Journal of Primary Health Care and General Practice*, 1(2).
61. Sathiyaseelan, T. & Gnanapala, W. K. A. C., 2015. Service Quality and Patients' Satisfaction on Ayurvedic Health Services. *American Journal of Marketing Research*, 1(3), pp. 158-166.
62. Saunders, M., Lewis, P. & Thornhill, A., 2019. *Research Methods for Business Students*. 8th ed. s.l.:Pearson Education Limited.

63. S. & B., 2016. *Research Method for Business*. 7 ed. New Delhi, India: Willey.
64. S. D., 2022. s.l.:s.n.
65. Smith, K., 2017. *Sri Lanka population*, s.l.: Slideshare.
66. Sohail, M. S., 2003. Service quality in hospitals: more favourable than you might think. *Managing Service Quality*, 13(3), pp. 197-206.
67. Subiyakto, B., Kot, S. & S. S., 2020. The Government Reform on Healthcare Facilities from the Standpoint of Service Quality Performance. *International Journal of Economics and Finance Studies*, 16(31).
68. Tantarto, T., Kusnadi, D. & Sukandar, H., 2020. Analysis of Service Quality Towards Patient Satisfaction (Comparative Study of Patients Using Telemedicine Application and Face to Face Consultation in Healthcare). *European Journal of Business & Management Research*, 5(5).
69. Teeling, S. P., Dewing, J. & Baldie , D., 2021. A Realist Inquiry to Identify the Contribution of Lean Six Sigma to Person-Centred Care and Cultures. *International Journal of Environmental Research & Public Health*, 18(10427).
70. TodayJaffna, 2020. *TodayJaffna*. [Online]
Available at: <https://www.todayjaffna.com>
[Accessed 25 12 2021].
71. T. S. S., 2022. *The Survey System*; [Online]
Available at: <https://www.surveysystem.com/sscalc.htm>
[Accessed 10 01 2022].
72. Unicef, 2021. *Key demographic indicators*, s.l.: Unicef for every child.
73. Velmurugan, G., Shubasini, R., Saravanabhavan, N. & Selvam, V., 2019. A Study on Service Quality of a Health Care Organization. *International Journal of Online & Biomedical Engineering*, 15(10), pp. 91-105.
74. Wanninayake , W. M. A. S., Mahakumbura, . M. & Hapugoda, . J. C., 2019. Perceived Service Quality & Customer Loyalty: An Application of SERVQUAL Model in Credits Card segment of Sri Lankan Private sector Banks. *Management Issues*, 4(1).
75. Westfall, P. H., Arias, A. L. & Fulton, L. V., 2017. Teaching Principal Components Using Correlations. *Multivariate Behavioral Research*, pp. 648-660.
76. WHO, 2010. *Health Service Delivery*, s.l.: World Health Organization.
77. Wijenayake, P., V, K., YJ, S. & MDU, G., 2019. Service quality of psychiatric care from patients'perspective; a descriptive cross sectional study conducted in National Hospital, Sri Lanka. *Galle Medical Journal*, 24(2), pp. 17-23.
78. Zaid, A. A. et al., 2020. The Impact of Total Quality Management and Perceived Service Quality on Patient Satisfaction and Behavior Intention in Palestinian Healthcare Organizations. *Technological Reports of Kansai University*, 66(3).

79. Zubayer, M. & Hoque, S., 2019. Healthcare Service Quality & In-Patients satisfaction: An Emprical Investigation on Healths Tangible Quality. *Global Journal of Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences*, 7(5), pp. 39-55.
80. Zun, A. B., Ibrahim, M. I. & Hamid, A. A., 2018. Level of Satisfaction on Service Quality Dimensions Based on SERVQUAL Model Among Patients Attending 1 Malaysia Clinic in Kota Bharu, Malaysia. *Oman medical Journal*, 33(5), pp. 416-422.

7 Appendix 1: Questionnaire

Name of the Student : Dr. Kanagaratnam Pakeerathan
ICBT ID : CL/CARDIFFMB/21/454
UWIC ID : 20192703
Name of the Supervisor : Mr. Ragukumar Thanganathan
MBA (Merit-Cardiff Met), MSc.IT (Distinction-Cardiff Met), BIT (UoC), MBCS,
CIMA Cert BA.
Senior Lecturer (IT & Management) |
Consultant Higher Education Management & Academic Affairs

Dear All,

I am Dr. Kanagaratnam Pakeerathan and Currently working as Medical Officer (MO) at Divisional Hospital Palai & also a Student of Cardiff Metropolitan University, UK. Presently reading for the Master of Business Administration (MBA) in Health Sector Management and as part of my study, I am doing research of Identification of factors that affect Healthcare Service Quality of OPD, DH Palai.

You are kindly invited to participate in this research. In this study, you are asked to complete the below attached questionnaire below. I highly appreciate if you could spend few minutes and fill the questionnaire at truthful manner which is used to gather primary data for my research.

I assure you that the Data gathered from you will not be provided to any other third party and strictly used only for my research. I further assure you that all your information provided will be treated confidentially and throughout the study approved ethical principles are maintained. I highly appreciate your generous cooperation in this regard.

Cardiff Metropolitan University

18.01.2022

Section one

Personal Details

Please answer all the questions by Cross (X) the box where it's appropriate

1. Gender

Male

Female

2. What is your age?

Under 18

19-25

26- 35

36-50

51-65

Over 65

3. What is your Marital Status?

Married

Widow

Divorced

Single

Don't want to Mention

4. How many Children are there in your family?

0

1-2

3-4

5-6

More than 6

5. What is your highest level of education?

Attended school

Diploma

Bachelor's Degree

Post Graduate

6. How would you describe your current employment status?

Un employment

Differently abled

Employed- Full Time

Employed- Part Time

Student

Home maker

Retired

7. How many years you working?

0

1-5

5-10

10-20

20-30

Above 30

8. How many times you have visited to DH Palai for OPD Services?

One time

Two times

Three Times

Many Times

9. In which of the following area do you live?

Urban/City

Rural

10. What's your Monthly Income?

<25000 Rs

25000-50000 Rs

50000-100000 Rs

100000-300000 Rs

>300000 Rs

Section Two

Please use the following Likert scale for the answering Section Two questions

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
1	2	3	4	5

Select one answer from above table 1 to 5 and mark it accordingly for the following queries 1 to 28.

No	Questions	1	2	3	4	5
Tangibility						
1	Using Modern Equipment; (Digital Thermometer, Pulse Oximeter ECG, X-ray Machine, Scan, Ambulance)					
2	Visually appealing Facilities (Fever Triage, Reception, Seating, Hand washing, Rest room, Separate Rooms for feeding mothers)					
3	Employees, who have a neat, Professional appearance (Uniform, wearing shoes with socks, wearing mask)					
4	Visually appealing materials associated with service (Instruction, direction, health banners, Name boards, Computers)					
Assurance						
5	Employees who instill confidence in patients (Be confidential)					
6	Making patients feel safe in their transactions (assure safety & security)					
7	Employees who are consistently courteous (have respect & be credible)					
8	Employees who have the knowledge to answer patients' questions (Be competent)					

Reliability					
9	Providing service as promised (Timeliness)				
10	Dependability in handling patients' service problems (consistency)				
11	Performing services right the first time				
12	Performing services as the promised time (Regularity)				
13	Maintaining error- free records (Accuracy)				
Responsiveness					
14	Keeping patients informed about when services will be performed (Doctors routines, cancellation of OPD service, health staff Strikes, Problem Solving)				
15	Prompt service to patients (Immediate Services)				
16	Willingness to help patients				
17	Readiness to respond to patients 'queries (Flexibility)				
Empathy					
18	Giving patients individual attention				
19	Employees who deal with patients in caring fashion				
20	Having the patient`s best interest at heart				
21	Employees who understand the needs of their patients (Right service)				
22	Convenient Service hours				
Service Quality					
23	Satisfaction (OPD services, Hygiene, Safety, Treatment Received,)				
24	Acceptance (what you have expected)				
25	Intention wants to Return (to receive the OPD service again)				
26	Convenience (Time, Flexibility, friendliness)				
27	No Complaints				
28	Recommend to Others (Word of Mouth)				

PARTICIPANT CONSENT FORM

Cardiff Metropolitan University Ethics Reference Number:

Participant name or Study ID Number:

Title of Project: Factors Influencing the Healthcare Service Quality: A Case Study on
Divisional Hospital-Palai OPD Services, Killinochchi District, Sri Lanka

Name of Researcher: Dr. Kanagaratnam Pakeerathan

Participant to complete this section	Please initial each box	
	Yes	No
I confirm that I have read and understand the information sheet for the above study.		
I have had the opportunity to consider the information, ask questions and have had these answered satisfactorily		
I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time, without giving any reason.		
I agree to take part in the above study.		
I agree to the interview / focus group / consultation being recorded		
I agree to the use of anonymised quotes in publications or I agree to my quotes being attributed to me		
I would like my organisations' name to be anonymised in all publications or I agree to my organisation being named in all publications		

Signature of Participant

Date.

Name of person taking consent

Date.

Signature of person taking consent

8 Appendix 2: Questionnaire (Tamil Version)

கேள்வித்தாள்

மாணவரின் பெயர் : வவத்தியகலாநிதி கனகரத்தினம் கெகீரதன்
ICBT ID : CL/CARDIFFMB/21/454
UWIC ID 20192703

மமற்றொர்வவயாளரின் பெயர்: திரௌ.ரகுமார் தங்கநாதன்

MBA (Merit-Cardiff Met), MSc.IT (Distinction-Cardiff Met), BIT (UoC), MBCS, CIMA Cert BA.

முதுநிலை விரிவுவரயாளர் (தகவல் பதாழில்நுட்பம் & மமலாண்வம)

ஆமலாசகர், உயர் கல்வி மமலாண்வம & கல்வி விவகாரங்கள்

அன்புள்ள அவனவருக்கும்,

நான் வவத்தியகலாநிதி கனகரத்தினம் கெகீரதன் மற்றும் தற்றமொதா வெள ஁ிரமதச வவத்தியசாவலயில் வவத்திய அதிகாரியாக ஁ணிபுரிகிமேன். மமலும் இங்கிலாந்து கார்டிஃப் பமட்மரா஁லிட்டன் ஁ல்கவலக்கழக மாணவனாகவும் உள்மளன். தற்றமொது சுகாதாரத் துவே நிர்வாகத்தில் முதுகவல வணிக நிர்வாகத்திற்கு (MBA) ஁லித்து வருகிமேன், மமலும் எனது கல்வியின் ஁ரு ஁குதியாக சுகாதார தரமசவவயில் தாக்கத்வத ஏற்றெடுத்தும் காரணிகள்: இலங்வக கிளிபநாச்சி மாவட்ட வெள ஁ிரமதச வவத்தியசாவல பவளிமநாயாளர் திவணக்கள மசவவகள் தவலப்டில் கு஁ித்த ஆராய்ச்சி பசய்து வருகிமேன்.

இந்த ஆய்வில் ஁ங்மகற்க உங்கவள அன்புடன் அவழக்கிமேன். இந்த ஆய்வில், நீங்கள் கீமழ இவணக்கப்ட்டுள்ள மகள்வித்தாவள பூர்த்தி பசய்ய மகட்கப்ட்டுகி஁ர்கள்.

நீங்கள் சில நிமிடங்கள் பசலவழித்து, எனது ஆராய்ச்சிக்கான முதன்வமத் தரவவச் மசகரிக்கப் ஁யன்஁டும் மகள்வித்தாவள உண்வமயான முவேயில் நிரப்டெ முடிந்தால் நான் உங்கவள மிகவும் ஁ாராட்டுகிமேன்.

உங்களிடமிர஁ந்தா மசகரிக்கப்ட்ட தரவு மவற஁ எந்த ம஁ன஁ம் தரப்ட்டினர஁க்கும் வழங்கப்ட்டாது என்று நான் உறுதியளிக்கிமேன்.கண்டிப்ட஁ எனது ஆராய்ச்சிக்கு மட்டுமம ஁யன்஁டுகி஁து. உங்களுக்கு வழங்கப்ட்ட அவனத்து தகவல்களும் ரகசியமாக நடத்தப்ட்டும் என்றும், ஆய்வு முழுவதும் அங்கீகரிக்கப்ட்ட பந஁ிமுவ஁க் மகா஁்ட்டுகள் ஁ராமரிக்கப்ட்டும் என஁றும் நான் மமலும் உறுதியளிக்கிமேன். இந்த விஷயத்தில் உங்கள் தாராளமான ஁த்துவழப்ட்வெ நான் மிகவும் ஁ாராட்டுகிமேன்.

கார்டிஃப் பமட்மரா஁லிட்டன் ஁ல்கவலக்கழகம்

18.01.2022

பகுதி ஒன்று

அவனத்த ு மகளவிகள ுக்க ும ெ பௌட்டரியில ெ பௌர ுத்தமௌ
இடத்தில ெ குேிக்கவும ெ

தனிப்பட்ட விவரங் ெள

1. ொலின

மீஆண்

பெண்

2. உங் ெள் வய F ெண் ன?

18 வய Fக்கு கீழ்

17-25

26- 35

36-50

51-65

65 வயதுக்கு ெ மமமல

3. உங் ெள் திருமண நிலை ெண் ன?

திர ுமணமௌவர்

விதவவ

விவாகரத்து

திர ுமணம்

ஆகவில்வல

4.உங்ேள் குடும்பத்திண் எத்தலன குழந்லதேள் உள்ளனர்?

0

1-2

3-4

5-6

6 க்க ு மமமல

5.உங்ேளின் மிே உயர்ந்த ேண்வி நிலை என் ன?

ெள்ளி கல்வி

டிப்ளமமா

இளநிவல ெட்டம்

முதுகவலப் ெட்டம்

6.உங்ேள் தற்கபாலதய கவலை நிலைய எவ்வாறு விவரிப்பீர்ேள் ?

மவவலவாய்ப்ெின்வம

மாற்றுத்திேனாளி

முழுமநர மவவல

ெகுதிமநர மவவல

மாணவரர்

வ஁ுப்ெணி

ஓய்வு பெற்ேவர்;

7. நீங்கள் எத்தனை ஆண்டுகள் வேலை செய்கிறீர்கள்?

0

1-5

5-10

10-20

20-30

30 க்கு மேல்

8. சேலிவநாயோளர் தினக்கள வணிகங்களில் பண பிரவதனத்தையோடு எத்தனை மூன்றுள்ளீர்கள்?

ஒரு முடிவு

இரண்டு முடிவு

மூன்று முடிவு

மேல் முடிவு

9. பின்வரும் எந்த பகுதியில் நீங்கள் வசிக்கிறீர்கள்?

நகர்ப்புறம்/நகரம்

கிராமப்புறம்

10. உங்கள் மாத வருமானம் என்ன? (இருவரும் சேர்த்து)

<25000

25000-50000

50000-100000

100000-300000

>300000

பகுதி இரண்டு

G+uzkhf Vw;Wf; nfhs;stpy;iy	Vw;Wf nfhs;stpy;iy	eLepyik	Vw;Wf nfhs;fpNwd;.	g+uzkhf Vw;Wf nfhs;fpNwd;
1	2	3	4	5

மமமல குேிப்பெிட்டுள்ள 1 இருந்து 5 வவர உள்ள ெதில்களில் பொருத்தமான ஒன்வேத் மதர்ந்பதடுத்து கீ மழ உள்ள 1 இருந்து 28 வவரயான மகள்விகளுக்கு பெட்டியில் குேி பசய்யுங்கள்.

இல	வகள்ேிக ள்	1	2	3	4	5
புண்களோல் உைரப்படும் சபோருட்கள்						
1	நவனீ உெகரணங்கவளப் ெயன்ெடுத்துதல்; (டிஜிட்டல் பதர்மமாமீட்டர், ெல்ஸ் ஆக்சிமீட்டர் ஈசிஜி, எக்ஸ்மர பமஷின், ஸ்மகன். ஆம்புலன்ஸ்)					
2	ொர்வவக்கு ஈர்க்கும் வசதிகள் (காய்ச்சல் சிகிச்வச, கணினிகளுடன் வரமவற்பு மசவவ, நாற்காலி, வக கழுவுதல், ஓய்வு அவே, தாய்மார்களுக்கான உணவு அவேகள்)					
3	ெணியாளர்கள், மநர்த்தியான, பதாழில்முவே மதாற்றேம் பகாண்டவர்கள் (சீருவட, சாக்ஸுடன் கூடிய காலணிகள் அணிதல், முகமூடி அணிதல்)					
4	மசவவயுடன் பதாடர்புவடய ெர்வவக்குஈர்க்கும் பொருட்கள் (அேிவுறுத்தல், திவச, சுகாதார ெதாவககள், பெயர் ெலவககள்)					
உறுதிசமோழி						
5	மநாயாளிகளிடம் நம்ெிக்வகவய வளர்க்கும் ெணியாளர்கள்					
6	மநாயாளிகள் தங்கள் ெரிவர்த்தவனகளில் ொதுகாப்பொன உணர்வவ ஏற்ெடுத்துதல்					
7	பதாடர்ந்து கண்ணியமாக இருக்கும் ெணியாளர்கள்					
8	மநாயாளிகளின் மகள்விகளுக்கு ெதிலளிக்கும் அேிவு உள்ள ெணியாளர்கள்					

நம்பகத்தன்மை						
9	வாக்குறுதியளித்தெடி மசவவவய வழங்குதல்					
10	மநாயாளிகளின் மசவவ ெரிச்சவனகவள வகயாள்வதில் நம்ெகத்தன்வம					
11	முதல் முவேயாக மசவவகவளச் சரியாகச் பசய்தல்					
12	வாக்குறுதியளிக்கபெட்ட மநரத்தில் மசவவகவளச் பசய்தல்					
13	ெவிவழ இல்லாத ெதிவுகவள ெராமரித்தல்					
சபோறுப்புைர்வு						
14	எப்தொது மசவவகள் பசய்யபெ்டும் என்ெது குேித்து மநாயாளிகளுக்குத் பதரியபெட்டுத்துதல் (மருத்துவர்களின் நவடமுவேகள், பவளிமநாயாளர் ெரிவுமசவவ ரத்து, சுகாதார ஊழியர்கள் மவவலநிறுத்தங்கள்)					
15	மநாயாளிகளுக்கு உடனடி மசவவ					
16	மநாயாளிகளுக்கு உதவ விருபெம்					
17	மநாயாளிகளின் மகள்விகளுக்கு ெதிலளிக்க தயார்					
பசெுதோபம்						
18	மநாயாளிகளுக்கு தனிபெட்ட கவனம் பசலுத்துதல்					
19	மநாயாளிகவள அக்கவேயுடன் வகயாளும் ெணியாளர்கள்					
20	மநாயாளியின் நலவன இதயத்தில் வவத்திருத்தல்					
21	தங்கள் மநாயாளிகளின் மதவவகவளப் புரிந்துபகாளளும் ஊழியர்கள்					
22	வசதியான மசவவ மநரம்					
வெனே தரம்						
23	திருப்தி					
24	ஏற்றுபகாளளாதல்					
25	மசவவவய மீண்டும் பெே ஆர்வம்					
26	வசதி					
27	புகார்கள் இல்வல					
28	மற்ேவர்களுக்குப் ெரிந்துவரக்க ஆர்வம்					

ஓப்புதல் பெறும் நெரின் பெயர்

திகதி

ஓப்புதல் பெறும் நெரின் வகையாப்தெம்

9 Appendix 3: Research Permission & Approval

பிரதேச வைத்தியசாலை – பணை
பிரதேச ரோகல - பලල
DIVISIONAL HOSPITAL –PALLAI
KILINOCHCHI

எனது இலக்கம் }
මගේ අංකය } N/P/04/45/P/H/P/208
My Number }

உமது இலக்கம் }
ඔබගේ අංකය }
Your Number }

திகதி }
දිනය } 18.01.2022
Date }

Dr.N. Saravanabhavan
RDHS
Office of the RDHS
Killinochchi

Dear Sir

I am an MBA in Health Sector Management student at Cardiff Metropolitan University, UK. The title of my thesis is **Factors Influencing the Healthcare Service Quality: A Case Study on Divisional Hospital-Palai OPD Services, Killinochchi District, Sri Lanka.**

Its aim is to study the Healthcare Service Quality of Out Patient Department (OPD) Services at DH Palai. As part of my research, I would like to undertake research with patients who are visiting to OPD at DH Palai. I am writing to you because OPD of DH Palai fits the profile of this type of organisation and this as to provide a large enough number of potential participants. This research project has received approval from Cardiff Metropolitan University and all data collection will be in accordance with the university's ethics code of practice.

My purpose in writing is to ask if you would permit me to issue a questionnaire to OPD Patients at DH Palai. Their participation would be entirely voluntary, neither their identity shall be presented in the research and it would only take 10 to 15 minutes for each patient to complete a questionnaire.

I shall be very happy to make the results of my research available to DH Palai & Office of the RDHS Killinochchi as a participant in the research when it is complete. If you would like to participate in this project and or are interested in discussing it further, please contact me on

University contact details
Cardiff School of Management
Cardiff Metropolitan University
Llandaff Campus, Western Avenue,
Cardiff, CF5 2YB
Tel: +44 (0)29 2041 XXX

Thank you in anticipation.
Yours sincerely

Approved with Ethical Clearance from the University

.....
Dr.N. Saravanabhavan
Regional Director of Health Service (RDHS)
Killinochchi, Sri Lanka. *Regional Director of Health Services Killinochchi.*

Dr.K. Pakeerathan
Medical Officer

Address: A 9, Road, Palai, Killinochchi, Northern Province, Sri Lanka

தொலைபேசி } பொது } 0212050025 மின்னஞ்சல் }
දුරකථන අංකය } පොදු } 0212283032 ඊ-මේල් }
Telephone No } General } E-Mail } palaidh@gmail.com

10 Appendix 4: Minutes of the Mandatory Supervisors Meeting

Dissertation – Meeting Record Sheet

RSU21

Name of the Student : Dr. Kanagaratnam Pakeerathan
 ICBT ID : CL/CARDIFFMB/21/454
 UWIC ID : 20192703
 Name of the Supervisor : Mr. Ragukumar Thanganathan
 MBA (Merit-Cardiff Met), MSc.IT (Distinction-Cardiff Met), BIT (UoC), MBCS,
 CIMA Cert BA.
 Senior Lecturer (IT & Management) |
 Consultant Higher Education Management & Academic Affairs

Date	Covered Topics/ Areas to improve	Signature of the Supervisor
15.12.2021 1 st Official Meeting	Discussed the General Research Proposal in detail, clearly decoded the rules and regulations established, gave the fruitful information & initial guidance, Learnt the ground rules & instructed basics of beginning part of the individual research including correction in the research title. Individually Advice to focus on Research title more clearly & research questions as well after my brief presentation. Asked to revisit the Annotated Bibliography and improve it. Fixed the deadline dates for our work. Gave the confident to proceed further. That was created the Enthusiasm on my research.	
11.01.2022 2 nd Official Meeting	Reviewed the Chapter one, observed the recorrected version of Chapter one, guided on RQ & RO, discussed all the doubt I had and guided me to the track. Advised to limit the wordcount of my chapter one. My Dilemma on Title & Research symptom & sign guided well and corrected. Discussed the Chapter Two, elaborated the important area of the Chapter Two and Brief out the Chapter Three. Asked to Prepare the Questionnaire. It was a Fruitful Discussion & pulled me to correct direction	
16.01.2022 (Individual Meeting)	Finalized the Questionnaire, Guided on Literature Review, Ethical Approval given. Asked to focus on wording.	
08.02,2022 3 rd & Final Official Meeting	Discussed the Fourth and Fifth Chapter in detail, Explained the Regression, Cronbach's Alpha, VIF, Skewness, Kurtosis Test, guided on Statistical Analysis and its interpretation,	
18.02.2022 Individual Final Review	Reviewed all the chapters carefully, asked to correct the page setting, table of content, guided to Durbin Watson statistical correlation, fine correction reviewed and asked to focus on such as standard statistical terminologies, concise writing. Advised on recommendation and future study. Suggested on audience-based recommendation towards WHAT & HOW approach.	

11 Appendix 5: Ethical Application Form

EXEMPLAR 1:

CARDIFF METROPOLITAN UNIVERSITY APPLICATION FOR ETHICS APPROVAL

When undertaking a research or enterprise project, Cardiff Met staff and students are obliged to complete this form in order that the ethics implications of that project may be considered.

If the project requires ethics approval from an external agency (e.g., NHS)

You will not need to seek additional ethics approval from Cardiff Met. You should however complete Part One of this form and attach a copy of your ethics letter(s) of approval in order that your School is aware of the project. The document *Ethics application guidance notes* will help you complete this form. It is available from the [Cardiff Met website](#). The School or Unit in which you are based may also have produced some guidance documents, please consult your supervisor or School Ethics Coordinator. Once you have completed the form, sign the declaration and forward to the appropriate person(s) in your school or unit

Participant recruitment or data collection MUST NOT commence until ethics approval has been obtained.

PART ONE

Name of applicant:	Dr. Kanagaratnam Pakeerathan
Supervisor (if student project):	Mr. Ragukumar S. Thanganathan MBA (Merit-Cardiff Met), MSc.IT (Distinction-Cardiff Met), BIT (UoC), MBCS, CIMA Cert BA. Senior Lecturer (IT & Management) Consultant Higher Education Management & Academic Affairs
School / Unit:	Cardiff School of Management, Cardiff Metropolitan University
Student number (if applicable):	20192703
Programme enrolled on (if applicable):	MBA in Health Sector Management
Project Title:	An Assessment on Factors Influencing the Healthcare Service Quality: A Case Study on Divisional Hospital-Palai OPD Services, Killinochchi District, Sri Lanka
Expected start date of data collection:	18 th of January 2022
Approximate duration of data collection:	10 Days
Funding Body (if applicable):	N/A

Does your project fall entirely within one of the following categories?	
Paper based, involving only documents in the public domain	No
Laboratory based, not involving human participants or human tissue samples	No
Practice based not involving human participants (e.g., curatorial, practice audit)	No
Compulsory projects in professional practice (e.g., Initial Teacher Education)	No
Project for which external approval has been obtained (e.g., NHS)	No
If you have answered YES to any of these questions, expand on your answer in the non-technical summary. No further information regarding your project is required. If you have answered NO to all of these questions, you must complete Part 2 of this form	
Other researcher(s) working on the project:	N/A
Will the study involve NHS patients or staff?	N/A
Will the study involve taking samples of human origin from participants?	No

In no more than 150 words, give a non-technical summary of the project
<p>Divisional Hospital Palai`s Healthcare service is one of the remarkable in the Pachchilaipalli, last few years its OPD Services used by patients are not satisfactory. Significantly its OPD patient`s turnover is reduced much low in last year 2021 as 13500. There could be many factors playing the role in reduction of the Patients, one is Poor Service Quality at OPD, where due to lack of healthcare staffs, infrastructure, attitudes of the staff, covid 19 & strikes of the healthcare professionals. several complaints & criticism made on News Papers Social Medias constantly on its Healthcare services. This study intended to focus on assessing the factors which are influencing the Healthcare Service of OPD at DH Palai and make feasible recommendations & find the strategies to Improve its Service Quality.</p>

DECLARATION:	
I confirm that this project conforms with the Cardiff Met Research Governance Framework. I confirm that I will abide by the Cardiff Met requirements regarding confidentiality and anonymity when conducting this project.	
STUDENTS: I confirm that I will not disclose any information about this project without the prior approval of my supervisor	
Signature of the applicant:	Date:19.01.2022
Dr. Kanagaratnam Pakeerathan	
FOR STUDENT PROJECTS ONLY	
Mr. Ragukumar S. Thanganathan MBA (Merit-Cardiff Met), MSc.IT (Distinction-Cardiff Met), BIT (UoC), MBCS, CIMA Cert BA. Senior Lecturer (IT & Management) Consultant Higher Education Management & Academic Affairs	Date:19.01.2022
Signature Supervisor:	
Research Ethics Committee use only	
Decision reached:	Project approved Yes
	Project approved in principle
	Decision deferred
	Project not approved
	Project rejected
Project reference number:	
Name:	Date:
Signature:	
Details of any conditions upon which approval is dependent:	

PART TWO

A RESEARCH DESIGN	
A1 Will you be using an approved protocol in your project?	No
A2 If yes, please state the name and code of the approved protocol to be used	
N/A	
A3 Describe the research design to be used in your project	
<p>This study based on Empirical research approach where primary data will be collected from the OPD Patients of DH Palai through the printed Survey Questionnaire. The Questionnaire will be formed based on Literature Review and Ethical Approval to conduct the study. Probably current Pachchilaipalli population 14504 will be considered as study population & OPD patients will be randomly selected to reach the minimum 374 sample size.</p> <p>Participants (including Parents or Guardian of the Children) voluntarily involve in the study and could withdraw from the study during any time of the research without any reason or can discuss their concern on study with researcher. If the Participant is Under 18, their parents or Guardian can fill the Questionnaire. Informed consent will be obtain & gathering data using such tool will be confidential & not used by third party under any circumstances.</p> <p>IBM SPSS version 26 statistical software & MS Excel will be used to analysis the data gathered and researcher will provide the possible recommendations based on findings.</p>	
A4 Will the project involve deceptive or covert research?	No
A5 If yes, give a rationale for the use of deceptive or covert research	
N/A	
A6 Will the project have security sensitive implications?	No
N/A	
A7 If yes, please explain what they are and the measures that are proposed to address them	
N/A	

B PREVIOUS EXPERIENCE
B1 What previous experience of research involving human participants relevant to this project do you have?
N/A
B2 Student project only
What previous experience of research involving human participants relevant to this project does your supervisor have?
Supervisor has many experiences on supervising several master students' research projects previously and successfully guided it.

C POTENTIAL RISKS
C1 What potential risks do you foresee?
Collecting data within stipulated time will be challenging and has high risk of Covid-19 Infection. and most of the OPD Patients are Children, hence their parents or guardian are only available resource person to collect the data, it is quite dilemma for the researcher to gather the comprehensive information.
C2 How will you deal with the potential risks?
Recommended protection measures will be practice throughout the data collection to minimize the risk of Covid 19 infection.

When submitting your application, you **MUST** attach a copy of the following:

All information sheets

Consent/assent form(s)

An exemplar information sheet and participant consent form are available from the Research section of the Cardiff Met website.

12 Appendix 6: Saunders's Research Onion

(Saunders, et al., 2019)

13 Appendix 7: Healthcare Delivery Model in Sri Lanka

Source: (Smith, 2017)